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D7.2-Methodological framework for the socio-economic assessment of adaptation measures to climate change

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning / Full text
ABS	Increase in social Benefits
AHP	Analytic Hierarchy Process
CCLLs	Coastal City Living Labs
CBA	Cost-Benefit Analysis
CBR	Cost-Benefit Ratio
CBSM	Community Based Social Marketing
CEA	Cost-effectiveness analysis
CICES	Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services
EbA	Ecosystem-Based Approach
EEA	European Environmental Agency
ENoLL	European Network of Living Labs
ENPV	Economic Net Present Value
ESS	Ecosystem Services
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GIS	Geographic Information System
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
MCA	Multiple-criteria analysis
MCDA	Multiple criteria decision analysis
MVP	Minimal Viable Product
NPV	Net Present Value
RCP	Representative Concentration Pathways
SMCDA	Spatial Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis
SRRI	Social Rate of Return on Private Investments
S RTP	Social Rate of Time Preference
SUDS	Sustainable Drainage System
TCM	Travel Cost Method
WACP	Weighted Average Cost of Capital
WP	Work Package
WTP	Willingness To Pay

BACKGROUND: ABOUT THE SCORE PROJECT

SCORE is a four-year EU-funded project aiming to increase climate resilience in European coastal cities.

The intensification of extreme weather events, coastal erosion and sea-level rise are major challenges to be urgently addressed by European coastal cities. The science behind these disruptive phenomena is complex, and advancing climate resilience requires progress in data acquisition, forecasting, and understanding of the potential risks and impacts for real-scenario interventions. The Ecosystem-Based Approach (EbA) supported by smart technologies has potential to increase climate resilience of European coastal cities; however, it is not yet adequately understood and coordinated at European level.

SCORE outlines a co-creation strategy, developed via a network of 10 coastal city 'living labs' (CCLs), to enhance coastal city climate resilience rapidly, equitably and sustainably through EbAs and sophisticated digital technologies.

The 10 CCLs involved in the project are: Sligo and Dublin, Ireland; Vilanova i la Geltrú/Province of Barcelona, Benidorm and Oarsoaldea, Spain; Oeiras, Portugal; Massa, Italy; Piran, Slovenia; Gdańsk, Poland; Samsun, Turkey.

SCORE will establish an integrated coastal zone management framework for strengthening EbAs and smart coastal city policies, creating European leadership in coastal city climate change adaptation in line with The Paris Agreement. It will provide innovative platforms to empower stakeholders' deployment of EbAs to increase climate resilience, business opportunities and financial sustainability of coastal cities.

The SCORE interdisciplinary team consists of 28 world-leading organisations from academia, local authorities, RPOs, and SMEs encompassing a wide range of skills including environmental science and policy, climate modelling, citizen and social science, data management, coastal management and engineering, security and technological aspects of smart sensing research.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is a deliverable of the SCORE project, funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003534.

The main aim of this document is to present the results of WP7's task 7.2, notably regarding the development of a methodological framework for the socio-economic assessment of adaptation measures to climate change, particularly ecosystem-based approach (EbA) solutions, within the CCLLs of the SCORE project. Based on the findings of the systematic literature review presented in D7.1 (Riera-Spiegelhalder et al., 2022), multiple criteria analysis (MCA) is the method selected to perform a participatory-based assessment in the upcoming task 7.3 while a Cost-benefit analysis (CBA) is proposed for an expert-based approach associated with task 7.4. Both methods integrate the ecosystem services approach within the analysis.

The MCA is intended to involve local and regional stakeholders of the ten CCLLs in the evaluation of adaptation solutions through the development of interactive activities such as workshops. The CBA is planned to be carried out by WP7 researchers in the four CCLL frontrunners (Sligo, Ireland; Piran, Slovenia; Oarsoaldea, Spain; Vilanova i la Geltrú/Province of Barcelona, Spain).

This report presents the general guidelines to implement both types of assessments, which will be adapted to the local specificities, in terms of the definition of the intervention area, main climate hazards and climate sectoral impacts to be addressed, and EbA interventions to assess in the following tasks (Tasks 7.3 and 7.4).

LINKS WITH OTHER PROJECT ACTIVITIES

As part of a continuous process, the work developed by **WP7** is directly connected with the procedures of other WPs, in terms of technical (or methodological) and governance aspects.

When it comes to the **methodological** connections, information provided by **WP1**, notably the identification of key hazards and their map representation for each one of the CCLLs, will serve as a basic input for the socioeconomic analysis. The EbAs under scrutiny in the MCA and CBA will be selected in terms of their suitability to be used as effective solutions to the identified hazards.

The work produced by **WP3** is also relevant for the development of the CBA analysis. The climate change projections generated by the WP3 models at the urban scale level will be able to provide scenarios that will inform and allow us to detect which will be the level of impact of the identified hazard. For instance, if coastal erosion is the identified hazard, the model will be able to predict the level at which the sea level will arise according to different climate change scenarios. By having these projections, WP7 can identify variables that can be monetized that are directly related to the hazard and the performance of EbAs (e.g., damage loss avoided with adaptation). For this purpose, WP7 will work with **WP6**, which will also estimate monetary losses associated with the risk of certain hazards. This type of information could be integrated in the CBA developed in WP7.

WP7 will also feed the ICT platform developed under **WP5** by providing all the data derived from the socio-economic assessments done. This link will be particularly relevant during the implementation of the MCA (Task 7.3), and the CBA (Task 7.4). All the results collected at the different CCLLs will be transferred to WP5 to include them in the digital catalogue.

From a **governance** perspective, a diverse set of EbAs will be evaluated by the CCLLs' stakeholders, notably through an MCA approach considered in WP7. This type of participatory-based assessment connects directly with **WP2**, as

the identification and mapping of stakeholders is one of the main steps to formalize a Living Lab, which is the governance model that will be implemented in each of the cities. Next table summarizes the links explained above.

Table 1: WP7 links to other WPs

<u>Technical</u>	WP1	WP3	WP5	WP6
WP7	The socio-economic impacts will be evaluated in terms of the identified hazards by WP1	The predictions generated by the models Will create the counter factual scenarios that will be used to compare as part as the CBA analysis.	Data collector. Pre/post EBA intervention evidence collection and Marketplace	The methodology developed in order to calculate risk management, where the monetization of non-market prices is conducted
<u>Governance</u>	WP2			
WP7	The selection of the EBA Will be conducted as a participatory process where the identification of stakeholders is extremely important			

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5. INTRODUCTION

This report presents a methodological framework for the socio-economic assessment of EbA interventions, including a participatory and an expert-based approach. This document is the main output of WP7's task 7.2 - "Development of a methodological framework for the socio-economic assessment of adaptation measures to climate change".

The participatory approach targets local and regional stakeholders from the CCLLs, including representatives from citizens, government, academia, and industry. The main objective of this type of assessment is to involve these stakeholders in the socio-economic analysis of EbA, from the identification and validation of potential interventions to their ranking and prioritization. Gender, culture, and class balance of the selected actors are considered, so that the results of the participatory approach be representative. This analysis is designed to be suitable to all CCLLs' stakeholders, with low to medium knowledge, technical, time and cost requirements.

The expert-based approach refers to a more comprehensive socio-economic assessment, aimed at quantifying and evaluating the costs and benefits associated to the assessed EbAs. This approach also considers the environmental and social impacts of the adaptation options assessed, measured in terms of ecosystem services losses or gains. This type of assessment is intended to be implemented by researchers and experts, since it presents a higher level of complexity, in terms of technical knowledge and data requirements than the participatory-based assessment.

Following the results from the systematic literature review of socio-economic assessment methods of adaptation measures to climate change done in Task 7.1 (D7.1 – Synthesis of socio-economic assessment methods, databases, and studies addressing EbA and other adaptation strategies; Riera-Spiegelhalder et al., 2022), two different methods have been selected for these approaches:

- **Multiple criteria analysis (MCA)** is considered as an appropriate method for the participatory-based assessment as it allows to integrate stakeholders in the different MCA stages, including the evaluation and prioritization of adaptation measures. MCA goes one step further than monetary-based methods such as CBA or Cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA) as it additionally allows to integrate non-monetary metrics associated with different socioeconomic and environmental categories (e.g., governance, adaptation effectiveness, environmental impacts, etc.). MCA is a useful participatory-based tool to solve complex decision problems, allowing individuals to compare different options, according to pre-defined criteria and to come up with an overall score for each option, thus being able to prioritize them.
- **Cost-benefit analysis (CBA)** was selected to assist the expert-based assessment of EbAs. CBA is a socio-economic assessment tool that decision-makers often rely on to value and compare different adaptation measures and to make public choices (André et al., 2016). Adaptation measures are prioritized in terms of an economic efficiency criteria, i.e., the maximization of the difference between benefits and costs expressed in monetary terms. In comparison with classic CBA, which only includes market-related costs and benefits, the social CBA also considers non-market costs and benefits.

Table 2 shows an overview of the main differences between MCA and CBA within the context of the socioeconomic assessment of EbA solutions in the CCLLs. These features are further developed in sections 8 and 9 of this report.

Table 2: Summary of main differences between MCA and CBA

Features	MCA	CBA
CCLLs involved	Frontrunners and followers (n=10)	Frontrunners (n=4)
Level of complexity (Knowledge, technical skills, time, and cost requirements)	Low	High
Type of assessment	Participatory	Expert-based
Agents to apply the method	Practitioners/Academicians	Academicians
Stakeholder involvement	Yes	No
Adaptation measures assessed	EbA	EbA, ensuring the potential comparability of the results with other studies assessing EbA and hard interventions

After defining the guidelines for the application of both methods in the current deliverable, the MCA will be implemented in the ten CCLLs (Task 7.3; M13-M42) and the CBA will be conducted in the four frontrunner CCLLs of WP7 (Piran, Slovenia; Sligo, Ireland; Oarsoaldea, Spain; and Vilanova i la Geltrú/Province of Barcelona, Spain) (Task 7.4; M13-M42).

The remainder of this document is structured as follows. **Section 6** presents the case study areas where both methods will be applied. **Section 7** provides an overview on how ecosystem services are addressed within both methodologies. **Sections 8** and **9** describe the aim and guidelines for implementing MCA and CBA, respectively, within the SCORE's CCLLs. **Section 10** includes final remarks related to uncertainty, adaptability, and replicability of the proposed methods.

6. CASE STUDY AREAS

The SCORE project relies on the CCLL approach to select the case study areas. The concept of Living Lab is a step forward towards site specific co-design and co-creation of interventions, activities, and solutions. The following definition of a CCLL will be used in the SCORE project, expanding the concepts of living labs to a wider vision for coastal cities and settlements.

A coastal city living lab is an innovation intermediary which orchestrates an ecosystem of actors in a specific coastal region to tackle specific challenges related to sea level rise, coastal erosion, and extreme events.

Within ten different coastal cities across Europe (Figure 1), stakeholders from citizens' groups, academia, government, and industry institutions take part on an integrative process to define the problem space, co-design the solution plan, pilot the interventions and evaluate the performance of coastal city EbA interventions.

The ten CCLLs are grouped in frontrunners or followers if they satisfy certain criteria. The expert-based approach is to be tested on the frontrunners CCLLs, and the participatory method on either the frontrunners, or the followers. The selection criteria to evaluate the CCLLs, and assess whether these can be considered frontrunners are: availability of studies that provide a socio-economic analysis of the impact and adaptation to climate change in the geographical area; the existence of local/regional strategies or plans focused on climate

change adaptation in the area; the availability of socio-economic assessment tools in the CCLLs; skills and technical knowledge related to the implementation of socio-economic assessment of EbAs; adaptation measures to climate change already implemented in the CCLLs. Based on these criteria, four locations are considered frontrunners for this analysis: Vilanova i la Geltrú – Province of Barcelona (Spain), Oarsoaldea (Spain), Piran (Slovenia) and Sligo (Ireland). The remainder CCLLs, namely Benidorm (Spain), Dublin (Ireland), Gdańsk (Poland), Massa (Italy), Oeiras (Portugal), and Samsun (Turkey) are then followers. Section 6.3 provides a general overview of the ten CCLLs with their main characteristics, and section 6.4 follows with a general description of the ten areas of study.

Figure 1: CCLLs locations

Legend: 1. Oeiras (Portugal); 2. Oarsoaldea (Spain); 3. Vilanova i la Geltrú/Province of Barcelona (Spain); 4. Benidorm (Spain); 5. Sligo (Ireland); 6. Dublin (Ireland); 7. Massa (Italy); 8. Piran (Slovenia); 9. Gdańsk (Poland); 10. Samsun (Turkey).

6.3. CCLLs general overview

Table 3 provides a general overview of the main characteristics of the ten CCLLs, notably: the name of the study area and the corresponding surface (in km²); the coastal length (in km); number of inhabitants; role of the CCLL within WP7; and the type of socio-economic assessment to be done.

Table 3: Main characteristics of the CCLLs

CCLL	Country	Coastal area (name and length in km)	Area covered by CCLL (km ²)	Population (No of inhabitants)	Role of the CCLL in WP7	Socio-economic assessment
Benidorm	Spain	Benidorm, 12km	38.51km ² (municipality)	67,588	Follower	MCA
Dublin	Ireland	Dublin Bay, 10km	922km ² (county area)	2,1 million	Follower	MCA
Gdańsk	Poland	Gdańsk Bay, 19.1 km	262km ² (city)	628,000	Follower	MCA

CCLL	Country	Coastal area (name and length in km)	Area covered by CCLL (km ²)	Population (No of inhabitants)	Role of the CCLL in WP7	Socio-economic assessment
Massa	Italy	Marina di Massa, 9km	93.84km ²	70,000	Follower	MCA
Oarsoaldea	Spain	East coastline of Guipúzcoa province; 6.5km	111.9km ²	71,759	Frontrunner	MCA CBA
Oeiras	Portugal	Tagus River estuary; 9km	46km ²	171,767	Follower	MCA
Piran	Slovenia	Littoral coast/Karst; 17km coastline in the municipality	44,6km ² (municipality)	18,500	Frontrunner	MCA CBA
Sligo	Ireland	County Sligo, 11km	1,838 km ²	65,535	Frontrunner	MCA CBA
Samsun	Turkey	Kızılırmak Delta; 45-50km	9,579km ² (province)	600,300	Follower	MCA
Vilanova/Province of Barcelona	Spain	Vilanova i la Geltrú: 7 km; Province of Barcelona: 101 km	Vilanova i la Geltrú: 33.99 km ² ; Coastal municipalities in the Province of Barcelona: 2,478.65 km ²	Vilanova i la Geltrú: 67,086; Coastal municipalities in the Province of Barcelona: 2,623,506	Frontrunner	MCA CBA

Table 4 and Table 5 summarize the natural or climate change related hazards and impacts that the coastal cities are facing, respectively. This information is based on the results provided by WP1, notably about the mapping of the baseline exposure and risk of extreme climate impacts on the 10 CCLLs.

Table 4: Natural or climate change-related hazards on the CCLLs

COASTAL CITY	Natural or climatic related hazards that affect the area							
	Coastal flooding	Land flooding	Landslide	Heatwave	Drought	Storm surge	Coastal erosion	Others
BENIDORM	X					X	X	
DUBLIN	X	X	X	X		X	X	Sea level rise
GDAŃSK	X	X						
MASSA	X	X				X	X	
OARSOALDEA	X	X	X			X	X	
OEIRAS	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
PIRAN	X			X	X	X		
SLIGO	X	X					X	
SAMSUN	X	X					X	
VILANOVA I LA GELTRÚ	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	

Source: Laíño Rebollido & Iglesias Rodríguez (2021).

Table 5: Climate change extreme impacts on the CCLLs

COASTAL CITY	Impacts of these hazards to the area						
	Tourism	Cultural heritage	Commercial buildings	Residential buildings	Energy networks	Transport networks	Others
BENIDORM	X	X		X			
DUBLIN	X	X	X	X	X	X	
GDAŃSK	X	X	X	X	X	X	
MASSA	X	X	X	X			
OARSOALDEA	X	X	X	X	X	X	
OEIRAS	X	X	X	X	X	X	
PIRAN	X	X		X		X	Fresh water access
SLIGO	X	X	X				
SAMSUN		X					Agricultural stress
VILANOVA I LA GELTRÚ	X	X	X	X	X	X	

Source: Laíño Rebollido & Iglesias Rodríguez (2021).

6.4. CCLLs basic description

This section presents a basic description for the CCLLs according to the results presented in Deliverable 2.1 General frontrunner CCLL operational plans, which correspond to the work developed by WP2 partners and CCLLs' members during the first year of the SCORE project. This description includes, among others, the location, the main geographical features, and the main hazards and related impacts affecting the study area.

Benidorm (Spain)

Benidorm CCLL, located in the east of Spain, has 67,588 yearly inhabitants, with more than 400,000 summer inhabitants due to tourism. Benidorm's CCLL leader is University of Alicante, supported by Benidorm's City Council.

Benidorm is located at 15 meters above sea level, in front of a beautiful bay on the Mediterranean coast. The bay was divided in two beaches by a rocky point and facing south. It is surrounded by mountains that protect it from the prevailing winds from the East and the cold from the North, resulting in an extremely mild climate, especially in spring, winter, and autumn.

The main natural or climatic-related hazards that affect the area are coastal floods, coastal storm surge and coastal erosion. All of these hazards have a direct impact on tourism, cultural heritage, and residential buildings (Laíño Rebollido & Iglesias Rodríguez, 2021).

Dublin (Ireland)

Dublin CCLL is located on Ireland's east coast, and it has 2.1 million inhabitants. Dublin's CCLL lead partner is University College Dublin, supported by Dun Laoghaire Rathdown County Council.

Dublin is the capital of Ireland, a country that has suffered a significant development after its introduction to the European Union (EU) in 1973. The Dublin Bay, which has a width of 10 km and a length of 7 km goes from the cape of Howth, located in the north at Dalkey Point, all the way to the centre of the city.

The main natural or climatic-related hazards that affect the area of the CCLL are landslide, heatwave, drought, coastal storm surge, coastal erosion, and sea-level rise. These have a direct impact on tourism, cultural heritage,

commercial buildings, residential buildings, and energy and transport networks.

Gdańsk (Poland)

Gdańsk CCLL is located on Poland's north coast, and it has 628,000 inhabitants. The lead partner of this CCLL is the University of Gdańsk.

Gdańsk is located at an altitude of 0-180 m above sea level. The longitudinal extent of the city is 19.1 km and the latitudinal is 33.9 km. This city is located on the Gulf of Gdańsk, at the mouth of the Motława River to the Martwa Wisła River, another larger stream is the Radunia Canal flowing into the Motława River.

The main natural or climatic-related hazards that affect the area of the CCLL are coastal floods and land floods, which have a direct impact on tourism, cultural heritage, commercial buildings, residential buildings, and energy and transport networks.

Massa (Italy)

Massa CCLL is in Italy's north-west, and it has 70,000 inhabitants. Progecom is the CCLL's main partner, with support from Lamma and the Municipality of Massa.

The coastal area of the Municipality of Massa is an extremely fragile territory from a hydrogeological point of view and is also very densely populated. The population density is 728 inhabitants/km², which grows significantly during summer months due to the large influx of tourists. Climate change has caused extreme conditions, such as sudden and heavy precipitations and prolonged irregular weather conditions.

The main natural or climatic-related hazards that affect the area of the CCLL are coastal floods, land floods, coastal storm surge and coastal erosion. Which have a direct impact on tourism, cultural heritage, and both commercial and residential buildings.

Oarsoaldea (Spain)

Oarsoaldea CCLL is located in the north of Spain and it has 71,759 inhabitants. The leader of the CCLL is Oarsoaldea Development Agency, supported by Naider.

The study area is a fragile territory with regards to climate change due to several reasons. Firstly, urban areas and business facilities are located right along the coastline (buildings, houses, roads, etc.), thus there is an increasing risk of suffering economic losses due to sea level rise, flooding, erosion, and coastal storms. Secondly, Oarsoaldea's port, Pasaia Port, is a key part of Europe's supply chain for iron, steel, and car industries, thus the reduction of the port operability due to the above-noted effects would have substantial economic and social consequences. Thirdly, aquifers and water reservoirs that supply water to most part of the local population could be affected due to storms and droughts. Fourthly, the Basque coastline is a highly green territory in terms of forests and protected areas (e.g., Jaizkibel, Peñas de Aia); climate change will increase the number of wildfires in these valuable areas, thus affecting the local flora and fauna. Finally, the Basque Country attracts several tourists over the year; their presence and impact on the local economy has been affected due to climate change.

The main natural or climatic-related hazards that affect the area of the CCLL are coastal floods, land flood, landslide coastal storm surge and coastal erosion. These hazards have a direct impact on tourism, cultural heritage, energy networks, transport networks and both commercial and residential buildings.

Oeiras (Portugal)

Oeiras CCLL is located in the western part of the Metropolitan Area of Lisboa, and it has 171,767 inhabitants. IST-ID is the CCLL lead partner, with support from Oeiras Municipality.

In Oeiras, there are many facilities along the shore that are often exposed to coastal storms. Those facilities include roads, the railway from Lisbon to Cascais, several kilometres of pedestrian's paths, historical monuments, among others. Occasionally, the combination between storms and high tides derives in an urban drainage system malfunction. The Municipality also has some problems with flooding of areas along the rivers where some buildings and assets are located. Due to the rainfall decrease that is already affecting Portugal, Oeiras region is also expected to suffer more severe and frequent droughts.

The main natural or climatic-related hazards that affect the area of the CCLL are coastal floods, land floods, landslides, heatwaves, droughts, coastal storm surge and coastal erosion. These hazards have a direct impact on tourism, cultural heritage, energy networks, surface water availability and quality, transport networks, and both commercial and residential buildings.

Piran (Slovenia)

Piran CCLL is located on the Slovenian coast in the southwest region of the country. It rises from 0 to 289 meters above sea level. The town of Piran has roughly 3,800 inhabitants and a relatively large number of non-permanent residents. The entire municipality of Piran that extends into the hinterland has 18,500 inhabitants. This CCLL is led by ZRS (Science and Research Centre Koper).

Piran, known as “the city of salt”, is a relatively small town with a rich cross-cultural history along the Adriatic coast. For more than 500 years Piran was part of the Republic of Venice, which is pronounced in the town's architecture. The city's coastal position in combination with its cultural heritage are the main attraction for tourism. However, in the summer tourist season, a rise in the demand for fresh water is evident, that burdens the existing scarcity of water for consumption. The main source of fresh water for the entire Slovenian coast including Piran, is from the river Rižana, which originates in the geological intersection between flysch and limestone. This source of fresh water is threatened by risks of pollution along the main transport routes through old infrastructure, and there is no reliable alternative source of fresh water for the area.

The main climatic-related hazards that affect the area of the Piran CCLL are coastal storm surges, coastal floods, heatwaves and droughts. These hazards have a direct impact on everyday life, and the major economic input that is tourism. Cultural heritage sites, transport networks and residential buildings are also impacted by these climatic hazards.

Sligo (Ireland)

Sligo CCLL is in the northwest of Ireland, and it has 65,535 inhabitants (2016). This CCLL is led by ATU Sligo, with support from Sligo County Council.

Sligo is facing severe climate impacts, and there are three main coastal locations to consider in this matter: (1) Streedagh Beach, a 3 km long sandy beach located on the north-western shore of a sandbar linking Streedagh Point to an area known as Connor's Island, close to the village of Grange; (2) Dunmorán Strand, a 3 km long sandy beach with a significant dune habitat, set in a rural region in county Sligo; and (3) Enniscrone, a 5 km long sandy beach and extensive dune system, adjacent to the busy seaside town at the western end of county Sligo.

The main natural or climatic-related hazards that affect the area of the CCLL are coastal floods, land floods coastal storm surge and coastal erosion, all of which have a direct impact on tourism, cultural heritage sites and commercial buildings.

Samsun (Turkey)

Samsun CCLL is located on Turkey's northern coast, and it has 600,300 inhabitants. The CCLL's main leader is the University of Samsun.

The landscape in Samsun is extremely flat and is surrounded by wetlands. Due to these conditions, floods or sea-level rise can cause serious damage. Samsun has two dams, Derbent and Altinkaya, built on the Kizilirmak river. These dams storage flood waters that can come from the upstream of the river. However, dams also prevent efficient sediment movement that feed the delta. Therefore, it is important to examine any changes to the coastal line. Samsun's coastal region is a key natura site with rich biodiversity, and it includes a bird sanctuary whose borders are under international protection. In this respect, any scientific study to be done against climate change challenges in the study area is very important for the protection of this region. Further, this region has a substantial agricultural industry which is very important to the regional and national economy.

The main natural or climatic-related hazards that affect the area of the CCLL are coastal floods, land flood coastal and coastal erosion, all of which have a direct impact on the cultural heritage sites in Samsun.

Vilanova I la Geltru / Province of Barcelona (Spain)

Vilanova I la Geltrú CCLL is in the east of Spain, and it has 67,086 inhabitants. The main partner is ENT, supported by Vilanova I la Geltrú's City Council and Barcelona's Provincial Council.

The majority of the population lives in the city centre, but there are also several residential areas spread in the city's territory. The Garraf massif –in the northern half of the municipality– and the Plana del Garraf –in the southern half– are the main units that make up the geology and geomorphology of Vilanova i la Geltrú. Overall, the city is located at 22 metres above sea level, though the higher part of the city is at 300 m above sea level. The municipality of Vilanova i la Geltrú has more than 18,000 trees and 108,000 m² of green areas. Moreover, "Els Colls i Miralpeix" is a coastal and terrestrial natural area included in the Nature 2000 Network, and it is considered a Site of Community Importance (SCI) and a Special Protection Area for Birds (SPA). Moreover, Platja Llarga is a coastal area of about 10 ha located 3 km south of Vilanova i la Geltrú. This area is bounded on the north by the Barcelona-Tarragona railway line, on the south by the sea and on the west by the municipality of Cubelles, very close to the wetland of the mouth of the Foix River. It is part of an old area of wetlands and coastal dunes of the Foix River delta and is one of the last remaining natural areas of the old river delta. Finally, the "Costes del Garraf" marine area - which covers the coastal area between the municipalities of Castelldefels and Cunit - is included in the Nature 2000 Network and is considered a SCI and SPA. This area is notable for the presence of *Posidonia oceanica* and *Cymodocea nodosa* grasslands, which provide refuge for various species of fish and invertebrates.

The main natural or climatic-related hazards that affect the area of the CCLL are coastal floods, land floods, landslide, heatwave, drought, coastal storm surge and coastal erosion. These hazards have a direct impact on tourism, cultural heritage sites, energy, and transport networks and both commercial and residential buildings.

7. ECOSYSTEM SERVICES

7.3. Definition of ecosystem services

An ecosystem service (ESS) simply said is any benefit to humans that is provided from the natural environment and from a healthy ecosystem. In a more academic sense (Haines-Young & Potschin, 2018): 'an ecosystem service is defined as the contribution that ecosystems make to human well-being'. An ecosystem according to this definition is regarded as a living system, and therefore is not only limited to the natural world, e.g., specific habitats or combination of habitats (and the species there-in), but ecosystems can also be regarded as an urban or other infrastructural systems that include human societies interactive with their natural surroundings (e.g., CCLL). Thus, the services are the outputs of these ecosystems, whether natural, semi-natural or highly modified, that most directly affect the well-being of people.

7.4. Classification of ecosystem services

The ecosystem services that can be provided by the combined living systems are numerous. Hence, various classification systems for ecosystem services have been developed especially for the support of the decision-making process (see also Table 5, Selective list of ecosystem services assessment tools of Deliverable 7.1 in Mar Riera-Spiegelhalder et al. (2022)). The European Environmental Agency (EAA) developed and implemented the Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES), based on practical and comprehensive NATURA 2000 sites assessment, and not specifically from the perspective of decision-making processes. This international system was developed for reasons of coherency and standardization, but further than that, mapping and valuing ESS through a systemized process would yield better results (<https://cices.eu>). Hence, the CICES framework is proposed here.

The present introduction on ESS draws from the guidance on the application of the revised structure that is numbered version 5.1 (Haines-Young & Potschin, 2018). The developed classification systems have in common that the initial separation of ESS is more or less identical, and these are services that are: Provisioning; Regulating; Cultural; Supporting. The initial level of the CICES v5.1 only comprises three sections:

1. Provisioning services, cover all nutritional, non-nutritional material and energetic outputs from living systems as well as abiotic outputs (including water);
2. Regulating and maintenance services, cover all the processes in which living organisms can mediate or moderate the ambient environment that affect human health, safety or comfort, together with abiotic equivalents;
3. Cultural services, that are all the non-material, and normally non-rival and non-consumptive, outputs of ecosystems (biotic and abiotic) that affect physical and mental states of people.

The advantage of having the regulating and maintenance (or support) services combined in the CICES v 5.1 is that the section now covers both the transformation and regulation of the physico-chemical and biological environments, as regulation and maintenance are often indiscernible at first glance. Especially concerning climate change actions, many related ESS, like the reduction of greenhouse gasses; carbon storage; erosion control; air purification; are contained in the section *Regulating and maintenance services*. Nevertheless, each section of the CICES v5.1 then gives rise to divisions, and subsequently groups, classes, and class types. An overview of the sections, divisions, groups with brief description is given in Table 6.

Table 6: Classification tree of ecosystem services according to CICES v 5.1

Section	Division	Group
Provisioning	Nutrition	Biomass
		Water
	Materials	Biomass, fibre
		Water
	Energy	Biomass-based energy sources
		Mechanical energy
Regulation & Maintenance	Mediation of waste, toxics and other materials	Mediation by biota
		Mediation by ecosystems

Section	Division	Group
	Mediation of flows	Mass flows
		Liquid flows
		Gaseous / air flows
	Maintenance of physical, chemical, biological conditions	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection
		Pest and disease control
		Soil formation and composition
		Water conditions
		Atmospheric composition and climate regulation
Cultural	Physical and intellectual interactions with biota, ecosystems, and land-/seascapes (environmental settings)	Physical and experiential interactions
		Intellectual and representative interactions
	Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with biota, ecosystems and land-/seascapes (environmental settings)	Spiritual and/or emblematic
		Other cultural aspects

The classification of ecosystem services provides a tool to discern various types of ecosystem services, however, other than being iterative, the ecosystem services assessment tools do not particularly provide a method to actively link the services to a living system, nor to identify the services provided within living environments, or by a particular EbA.

Thus, the following sections will provide two methodologies that enable the identification of the available ESS within a defined system or EbA: (1) *Correlation of the land/water surface with habitat, usage, and ESS*, through GIS mapping; (2) *Correlation of successful EbAs with previously identified provision of ESS*, where there is a focus on climate change adaptation measures.

7.5. Correlation of the land/water surface with habitat usage, and ESS

GIS that maps the use of the land surface in means of habitat it provides and the usage by humans, can link the soil surface to the provision of ESS. For example, Derkzen et al. (2015) quantified the urban ecosystem services based on high-resolution data of urban green space for the city of Rotterdam, The Netherlands. They used and compiled various high resolution GIS maps to make consecutive maps showing: trees; woodland; tall shrub; short shrub; herbaceous; garden; water; other. Through conversion equations, quantification of the contribution of each of these habitats to the following ESS became possible: air purification; carbon storage; noise reduction; run-off retention; cooling; recreation. The quantification was performed for each of the different district areas of the city. Eventually, the maps of the district areas gave rankings for: 1) their contribution to the city's total urban green space, and 2) besides, per district area indicated the relative supply of each ecosystem service. Hence, the mapping provides: **area-specific ESS contribution**, and **identifies the city's most green areas**.

Similar approaches have been described, and are possible, for areas wider than urban environments, but these require the availability of high-resolution GIS data. Interestingly, if for a bordered area sufficient high-resolution GIS data are available for different timepoints in the past, it is possible to geographically identify **trends** of available ESS capacity (in surface area) in a wider region (e.g., de Andrés et al., 2018). This is especially useful when **over time** climate change vulnerability needs to be assessed, e.g., for the observation of coastal erosion, frequency of flooding events, and the identification of vulnerable areas.

The GIS mapping approach can even be expanded to the surface of the sea, where shallow coastal waters considered for establishing EbA, have not fully revealed their seabed classification. For example, depending on the depth of the water it is possible to identify the presence of sea grass meadows (linked to ESS carbon storage and erosion control) using either sonar recordings or aerial photography (Poklar, 2020). With respect to SCORE CCLL's and their nearby seabeds where EbAs might be considered, the classification of underwater habitats can be an important tool as well.

7.6. Correlation of successful EbAs with previously identified provision of ESS

For coastal areas in general, with their specific climate change hazards and associated impacts, it is possible to prepare an overview of successfully implemented EbAs, and evaluate which ESS were provided and how efficiently hazards were addressed. A compilation of such overview could be performed on the EbA-overview in preparation from Table A 1. Summary of the main characteristics of the reviewed studies of **Deliverable 7.1**. "Synthesis of socio-economic assessment methods, database, and studies addressing EbA and other adaptation strategies" (Riera-Spiegelhalder et al., 2022).

The ESSs generally provided from EbAs (World Bank Group, 2021) are often categorized as *regulating and maintenance services*, depend on specific geographic and meteorologic circumstances, and considering CCLLs, depend on the specific urban and coastal settings. Thus, multiple EbAs can contribute to mitigation of the same climate change hazard. An overview might indicate which EbAs do contribute to reduce floodings or coastal erosions. Such an overview of EbAs and the correlated ESS, might rank EbAs in their efficiency, or facilitate ranking depending on specific CCLL characteristics.

To illustrate how that would look, Table 7 shows some common EbAs and lists their correlation with a non-exhaustive list of ESS they provide.

Table 7: Examples of the correlation between some common EbAs and ESS

ESS (examples)	Tree planting	Sea grass meadows	Sand dune restoration	Green rooftops
Provision of food and other resources	x	x		x
Climate regulation	x	x	x	x
Carbon storage	x	x	x	x
Run-off retention	x			x
Cooling	x			x
Habitat for species	x	x	x	
Erosion control		x	x	
Air purification	x			x
Recreation	x	x	x	x

7.7. The value of Ecosystem services as an asset for Climate Change Adaptation

Ecosystems and its associated services contribute to human well-being, survival, health and livelihoods (Carpenter et al., 2006; Sukhdev et al., 2010). The economic valuation of ecosystem services allows us to carefully consider them as inexhaustible and free resources and be aware of the cost of their loss and degradation (Costanza et al., 1997; Carpenter et al., 2006; Sukhdev et al., 2010; TEEB, 2011) in ecological, socio-cultural and economic terms. CBA is a useful tool to assist in decision making for climate change adaptation solutions and ecosystem conservation. The economic information, or monetary valuation, on ecosystem services allows us to identify where protection and restoration measures are more profitable and can be implemented at a lower value (Crossman & Bryan, 2009; Crossman et al., 2011). That is why **ecosystem services must be considered when analysing the cost-benefit of alternatives**. There is now substantial evidence describing how ecosystems can reduce impacts such as wave action, erosion, and flooding. These services can stand alone, but can also be incorporated into hybrid adaptation solutions, where ecosystems are utilized alongside engineered defences (coastal ecosystems: a critical element of Risk reduction, 2013).

The process of monetization of ecosystem services started in the 1960s, but began to grow years later, after the publication of (Costanza, et al., 1997). Since then, several articles and reports have been published on the monetary valuation of natural resources, ecosystem services and biodiversity.

Table 8: Examples of ecosystem-based typologies for the coastal conservation

Coastal area	Estuary	Rivers
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recovery and restoration of dune systems. - Regeneration of beaches through local transfer of sediment. - Planting of submerged aquatic vegetation to reduce wave energy. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recovery and stimulation of the natural dynamics of the estuary through the demolition of dykes and the creation of small streams to favour tidal exchange. - Creation of buffer zones with the objective of favouring the migration of the natural system, generating new flood zones, and allowing the buffering of extreme maritime events. - Protection and rehabilitation of the margins of the channels through the planting of marsh vegetation and the installation of natural materials, such as logs, oyster bags or mussels, among others. - Recovery of spaces occupied by landfills for the transformation of the surface into marsh areas. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Restoration/re-naturalization of degraded riparian spaces and stabilization of margins. - Elimination of longitudinal physical barriers to water and biological flow to improve the continuity of the riverbed. - Creation of controlled flood zones through partial flood control, lowering of the water level and removal of mottles. - Implementation of sustainable drainage systems (SUDS) to control runoff generated by flooding.

7.8. Considerations

It is important to note that both methodologies are not to be regarded as purely independent. In fact, the methodologies are mutually supportive and co-creative, and for our purpose can be used in combination, and as such can provide both high qualitative and quantitative data.

Certainly, the combination of methodologies is a good way of finding potential hot-spot areas for introducing EbAs depending on the CCLL-specific conditions.

The correlation of EbA and ESS (Section 7.6) can be performed before introduction to Focus Group Discussions are planned. Thus, presenting effective EbAs might give more direction to Focus Groups, so they are more purpose-directed. In other words, by presenting an overview might give fundamental knowledge to stakeholders correlated to the projected outcomes, by empowering stakeholders to act and select EbAs more specific to tackling the CCLL's specific hazards.

The correlation of land/water surface and ESS (Section 7.5) requires disclosure of high-resolution GIS photography, and is perhaps a more time-consuming exercise, especially when combining municipal maintenance maps, public works maps, plot boundary maps, and land use maps. Combining maps planned in WP1, WP3, WP5, could contribute valuable specific information to this Deliverable.

It needs to be noted especially that although each methodology can be independent, being virtually performed independent and/or in combination, the end-result ESS assessment of any urban or wider area, needs a proper validation from local experts and stakeholders, and cannot be implemented without such verification by local knowledge.

Finally, regarding the proposed EbAs, it needs to be considered that due to the implementation of any EbA, the use of land, soil or water might change (especially with large scale land transformation EbAs), and consequently the ESSs over time, might be considered differently in efficiency by various stakeholders. In addition, the methodologies presented here consider EbAs giving rise to predominantly *regulating and maintenance services*, however in doing so, especially to low-end stakeholders the value of *cultural ecosystem services* might be considered neglected, and depending on the quadruple helix model stakeholders, even *provisioning services* might be considered discriminated. Thus, monitoring of the correlation of EbAs and ESSs through stakeholder assessment over time is considered wise.

8. MULTIPLE CRITERIA ANALYSIS WITHIN SCORE'S COASTAL CITY LIVING LABS

One of the methods for assessing climate change adaptation actions, including ecosystem-based adaptations or EbAs, is Multiple criteria analysis (MCA). Also known as multiple criteria decision analysis (MCDA), MCA complements other assessment methods, such as cost-benefit analysis (CBA) and cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA).

This section has four main parts: (1) *Introduction to MCA*, including its definition, examples of application, overview of the main process, advantages, and limitations; (2) *Stakeholder engagement in MCA*, including its importance and how to select stakeholders; (3) *Stakeholder engagement tools and methods*, including an overview and how to select these tools and methods; and (4) *Step-by-step guidelines for MCA application*, including examples and templates.

8.3. Introduction to MCA

8.3.1. Definition of MCA

MCA aids the assessment of different policies, measures, or actions (hereinafter referred to as options) against a set of multiple qualitative and/or quantitative evaluation criteria. With the involvement of multiple stakeholders, including experts, MCA integrates both subjective and objective assessments. Overall, MCA provides a structured, transparent, and iterative framework wherein the decision problem is broken down into a process of multi-step, leading to a decision recommendation.

MCA contains three key components: (1) a set of options which need to be ranked or scored; (2) a set of criteria measured in different units; and (3) a set of performance measurements for each option against each criterion (Hajkowicz & Collins, 2006). All in all, the key output of an MCA is a 'single most-preferred option', a 'set of ranked options', a 'short list of options for further appraisal', or a 'characterization of acceptable or unacceptable possibilities' (Munaretto et al., 2014).

8.4. Application of MCA

The application of the MCA as a participatory assessment has been gaining prominence across different contexts (Gamper & Turcanu, 2007; Hajkowicz & Collins, 2006; Huang et al., 2011; Kiker et al., 2005). For climate change adaptation, MCA has been used at different geographical locations, spatial scales, and problem contexts (Munaretto et al., 2014). These include adaptation planning at different levels (de Bruin et al., 2009; UNFCCC, 2011) and for specific sectors, such as flood risk and water resource management (Haque et al., 2012; Qin et al., 2008).

For coastal areas, MCA has been applied to assess various adaptation options, including EbAs, that could address different climate change hazards and their associated impacts. See **Deliverable 7.1**. "Synthesis of socio-economic assessment methods, database, and studies addressing EbA and other adaptation strategies" (Riera-Spiegelhalter et al., 2022). In all these applications, multiple stakeholders were involved, ranging from public authorities and experts to citizens and citizen groups.

8.4.1. Process of MCA

Although there are different approaches to MCA, they share common features or elements (see Cinelli et al., 2022; Huang et al., 2011). The following section provides the main steps (see Haque et al., 2012; 2016; CLIMACT PRIO, 2015; Munaretto et al., 2014), while a detailed step-by-step guideline for applying MCA is provided under **Section of 8.7** of this document.

Step 0. Understanding the local adaptation context (to be further defined)

Climate change adaptation is site-specific, and, thus, it is important to understand the local context. In this step, it is then important to review previous, current, as well as future plans and strategies; to examine the available ecosystems and the ecosystem services provided; and to check the locations of hazards and impacts as well as the results of vulnerability assessments, if available.

Further, the main objective of the MCA process, as well as the desired outputs or results are made explicit. Objectives can be, for example, to identify a set of options that can serve as inputs for recommendation for EbAs that can be later implemented in the CCLs. In this regard, it is also important to understand which main stakeholders will be involved in the MCA process (See **Section 8.5**).

Step 1. Identifying a list of preliminary options

Adaptation options, including EbAs, can range from public investments and infrastructures to plans and regulations. Identification of adaptation options can then be drawn from a variety of sources, such as literature review, expert judgement, as well as through elicitation of stakeholder preferences (e.g., by conducting surveys or workshops, or a combination of these methods).

Developing a database or inventory of adaptation options, including EbAs, have served as reference for stakeholders involved in MCA applications (de Bruin et al., 2009). Ruangpan et al. (2021), for example, developed a database of EbA options which included the types of measures and projects, the hazards addressed, potential locations, affected areas, and land use types.

Step 2. Screening or feasibility assessment

In cases where there is a long list of potential adaptation options identified, screening or feasibility assessment should be undertaken to select a shortlist of options to take further into the assessment. There may be options that are impractical because they are capital intensive or technically complex. Further, there may be options that are similar to each other; hence, duplicates are eliminated.

A way of screening the adaptation options is using feasibility criteria, such as stakeholders' acceptability, technical feasibility, financial viability, and ease of implementation (UN HABITAT, 2014). Additionally, ensuring consensus among the involved stakeholders regarding the scoring or feasibility assessment, is important for this step.

Step 3. Defining evaluation criteria

In this step, criteria to measure the performance of the options are identified and selected in a participatory manner. Evaluation criteria – which can be quantitative and/or qualitative - can be economic (e.g., reduction of public costs), environmental (e.g., improvement of water quality), and social (e.g., enhancement of recreational opportunities), among other categories.

However, evaluation criteria should meet certain attributes, such as relevance; completeness; reliability; measurability; and non-redundancy. Here, stakeholders' perspectives are crucial, while a review of the literature or relevant secondary documents, can provide information on what evaluation criteria may be important for further inclusion.

Step 4. Scoring or assessment of options

This step involves scoring or assessment of each action against each criterion. This can be performed by experts who can score the actions based on their technical expertise. Impact studies and modelling exercises can also be used to inform the scoring. It is also important that the scores are based on an agreed and clearly understood scale.

As different evaluation criteria may have different measurement units, scores can be standardized to a common scale, e.g., 0 to 1, by using a simple min-max standardization technique presented in the formula below.

$$x' = \frac{x - \min(x)}{\max(x) - \min(x)}$$

where x' is the standardized value derived from subtracting the minimum score from the original value (x) and then dividing it with the result of the difference between the maximum and the minimum values.

Step 5. Weighting of evaluation criteria

Evaluation criteria have different importance among stakeholders. Weighting then entails assigning a value to a criterion to indicate the degree of importance. Individuals or stakeholder groups can provide a weight, showing relative importance. Alternatively, equal weights can also be provided to all the criteria.

The formula for calculating criteria weights is:

$$W_i = V_i / \sum_n V_i,$$

where W_i indicates the weight of criterion i ; V_i stands for the value assigned by stakeholders to criterion i ; Σ indicates the summation of values assigned by stakeholders to criteria; and n indicates the number of criteria.

Step 6. Ranking and prioritization of options

A typical approach for over-all ranking and prioritization is the use of weighted summation. First, each option is calculated based on their weighted scores. The formula for weighted scores is:

$$WS_j = W_i * S_{ji},$$

where WS_j stands for the weighted score of option j , W_i stands for the weight of criterion i , and S_{ji} stands for score of option j to criterion i .

Next, the final ranking of options is calculated using the weighted summation formula:

$$FS_j = \sum WS_{ji},$$

where FS_j refers to the final score of option j and Σ indicates the summation of weighted score of option j .

Step 7. Sensitivity analysis

Sensitivity analysis is conducted to examine how sensitive the results of the final ranking are, based on different input variables, such as the assessment scores and on the criteria weights. In an MCA application, sensitivity analysis can be conducted by making all criteria weights constant, except for the one that is being tested (Liquete et al., 2016). This step is undertaken to integrate uncertainty and accommodate diverging preferences among stakeholders.

8.4.2. Advantages of MCA

Advantages of applying MCA (Hajkowicz & Collins, 2006; Gamper & Turcanu, 2007; Munaretto et al., 2014) include the following:

- Participation of multiple stakeholders who bring in diverse perspectives, preferences, interests, and values.
- Integration of different kinds of knowledge – from scientific knowledge to local and traditional knowledge.
- Transparency and accountability, as stakeholders reveal preferences in a more direct way and bring a common understanding of problems and solutions.
- Learning through stakeholder dialogue and collective deliberation, as well as enables conflict resolution.

- Multi-dimensionality, as MCA allows for the inclusion of both quantitative and qualitative information, as well as a wide range of criteria.
- Systematic, flexible, and iterative process that allows continuous feedback across the different steps, as well as re-evaluation of options considering new information.

8.4.3. Limitations of MCA

MCA also has its limitations (Gamper & Turcanu, 2007; Hajkowicz & Collins, 2006; Munaretto et al., 2014), namely:

- The boundaries of participation, including the choice of stakeholders as well as the degree, type, and timing of involvement, may be a challenge.
- The mediation of stakeholder perspectives, preferences, interests, and values can lead to approximation, while decision-makers may prefer exemplary decisions.
- The transparency of the MCA process may also be a deterrent; stakeholders may be reluctant to participate and share their knowledge.
- There may be information bias from certain stakeholder groups, while there may be power dynamics at play.
- The process may be technically complex for some stakeholders, particularly in the assessment of options and weighting of criteria.
- The application can be resource-, data-, and time-intensive; as such, the structure and content of the MCA process may be simplified.

8.5. Stakeholder engagement in the MCA process

8.5.1. Importance of stakeholder engagement

Engagement, in this context, refers to the active participation of relevant and interested stakeholders in the MCA process. Stakeholders, or individuals and groups that have a common interest or stake in identifying, evaluating, and selecting adaptation options, can (in)directly influence decisions or be affected by them. Stakeholders can be distinguished between 'standard' (decision-makers, experts, planners, and analysts) and 'interest groups' (political parties, civic organizations, residents) (Lahdelma et al., 2000).

But how to ensure a diverse pool of stakeholders and which criteria should be taken into consideration when identifying the most relevant stakeholders that can be involved in the MCA process?

Diversity in general refers to the heterogeneity among stakeholders. Stakeholders can cover different dimensions, ranging from age, gender, ethnicity, cultural values, occupational background, and religious or political preferences. See Table 9 for dimensions of diversity and example of benefits to MCA process. One of the advantages of diversity is that different perspectives are discussed and considered. Diverse stakeholders offer a variety of perspectives based on their interests, values, and needs. Thus, different perspectives can result in a wide range of viable options.

Table 9: Dimensions of diversity and example of benefits to MCA process

Dimensions	Benefits
Age	Exploration of a wider frame of population is needed as different age groups experience and use the environment differently. Consequently, different perspectives of environment can create and address diverse needs during the MCA process.
Gender	Gender and LGBTQI identification may also affect how the environment is perceived by some stakeholders in terms of the adaptation approaches that may be generated. Therefore, an inclusive approach is applied to fully utilize the lived social experience of stakeholders, and their understandings of how the environment and their contribution to preserving it are meaningful.
Culture	Values, beliefs, and norms shaped by cultures might influence the way people think and behave. Thus, ensuring cultural diversity among stakeholders can increase the level of acceptability of the decisions taken during the MCA process and, therefore, benefit the future implementation of adaptation solutions.

Diverse backgrounds will have knowledge in different fields and subjects, as well as their own non-professional lived experience or ‘citizen science’. Therefore, a rich mutual exchange may augment the development of innovative options, through a bottom-up inclusive approach that can enhance the legitimacy and credibility of the process.

Aiming for balance among stakeholders will make the process of MCA more transparent. Balancing stakeholders means understanding and respecting the aspirations of all stakeholders involved in the MCA. There are numerous benefits that can be associated with an effective balance among the stakeholders’ interests. These include better decisions due to high-trust communication and growth of an inclusive-collaborative culture. Additionally, balancing the stakeholders’ interest may result in the generation of innovative ideas for the selection of adaptation measures, as relevant data and considerations can be introduced that might otherwise be unnoticed by only the experts.

Also, the future success of any adaptation effort is highly dependent on the engagement of the involved stakeholders, especially at the identification and evaluation of options. When there is a diverse group of stakeholders having different perspectives, goals, and ambitions (Lehtinen & Aaltonen, 2020), it is important that stakeholders are engaged to create dialogue, foster connections, build trust, and avoid conflicts.

8.5.2. Selecting stakeholders in the MCA process

According to the quadruple helix model (See Deliverable 2.1 General frontrunner CCLL operational plans), the four main stakeholders that can be involved in the MCA process are as follows:

1. Government and public sector: municipalities, authorities at various levels/sectors.
2. Industry and business: companies, industries, developers, SMEs, associations of business organizations.
3. Academia and universities: universities, academicians, scientists, educational organizations.
4. Civil society: non-government organizations, community associations, citizens.

Due to pragmatic reasons, it is possible that stakeholder participation may be limited (Harrison & Qureshi, 2000). Thus, clear selection criteria will be designed to prioritize MCA needs in alignment with stakeholder interest and availability. The Stakeholder Power Grid (Figure 2) is an effective tool to achieve the most desirable and achievable results.

Figure 2: Stakeholder power-interest grid

Focus on the most impactful stakeholders becomes clear through this mapping exercise. It further enhances the efficient use of time and resources by engaging in depth with the most interested, available, and resourced groups, in the specific steps of the MCA process. According to the stakeholder power-interest grid, there are four main categories of stakeholders based on their power and interest:

- Low interest and low power: For stakeholders with low interest and low power, one-way communication of essential information will likely be sufficient in most instances
- Low interest and high power: This group is more influential than the previous one. Although they still have a low interest, it is important to regularly monitor this group, keep them informed for critical information, and anticipate any interests or needs they may have
- High interest and low power: Although they may not be as influential as the next category of stakeholders, regular, robust and (possibly) two-way communication with this highly interested stakeholder group would be beneficial
- High interest and high power: This group is both interested and powerful and will require more resources to engage with effectively. This is the 'priority' grouping of stakeholders who will require regular, robust, two-way communication tactics

There are also some limitations that cannot be neglected, especially when stakeholder engagement involves the citizens. Public participation is difficult to take to the scale. As the process may interest populations at large or may involve broader geographical scales, the opportunity for participation needs to be rationalized in view of finite budgets and personnel capacity, without compromising diversity.

8.6. Stakeholder engagement tools and methods

8.6.1. Overview of tools and methods

There is a great variety of engagement tools and methods being developed from different fields and disciplines. It is important to highlight that not all the methods and tools for stakeholders' engagement are the same. Their scope of reach and responsibility, as well as their overall aim might be different (Williams et al., 2020). Additionally, each tool and method have its own strong points and limitations, as well as a specific format of produced result (INVOLVE, 2005).

Each step requires different inputs to reach its goal. It would be, therefore, misleading to use a single tool throughout the MCA process. For that reason, different tools, and methods for engaging the involved stakeholders are included in this guide. Lastly, it is important to highlight that more than one engagement tool or method can be proposed in several of the MCA steps. In those cases, the combination of different methods, or some of their elements, would be an option, taking always into consideration the overall goal that needs to be achieved through the stakeholders' involvement for each of the steps.

Table 10 below presents an overview of the engagement tools and methods that can be used for each of the MCA steps, including a brief description (Mendoza & Macoun, 1999; Hornecker, 2004; Durham et al., 2014; Engage 2020, 2014; UN HABITAT, 2014; Institute for Housing and Urban Development Studies (IHS) & Labor für Politik und Kommunikation (FLMH), 2017; Unalab, n.d.). Those tools and methods constitute the means with which effective stakeholder engagement can be achieved, delivering the initial set of outcomes (Durham et al., 2014).

Table 10: Overview of stakeholder engagement tools and methods

Steps	Tools and methods	Brief Description
Step 0: Understanding the local adaptation context	Focus Group Discussion	Focus Group Discussion is a qualitative method that is used for identifying participants preferences and opinions on certain topics as well as for evaluating them. It is a guided method, that is led by a moderator, who is leading the conversation among the participants, based on predefined themes and questions (interviewing). Focus Group Discussion is appropriate for small groups.
Step 1: Identifying a list of preliminary options	Brainstorming	Brainstorming is a tool that aims on assisting a group to rapidly produce ideas on a topic. This tool helps participant to quickly express their ideas, without any filtering and/or limitations. It is a way of letting the participants express themselves in a creative way, that might prove difficult in a different and/or bounded context.
	Idea Dashboard	The Idea Dashboard is a tool for idea creation on an early stage of a process. It is a worksheet, where initial ideas upon a topic are collected from all the participants, allowing different perspectives to be highlighted. It is a helpful tool for creating ideas, that can be adapted and improved during the idea creation process, also allowing participants to refine the collected ideas.
	Brainwriting	Brainwriting is a brainstorming method, that is also called 6-3-5. In this method, the ideas instead of being orally expressed in a conversation, they are silently written down by the participants. Only when participants are finished with their ideas, those are shared among the group. This brainstorming method is particularly appropriate for small groups. As the alternative name of the method suggest, the participants are asked to brainstorm on paper for six rounds (6), with a duration of five minutes each (5), producing three ideas (3).

Steps	Tools and methods	Brief Description
	Role storming	Rolestorming -or Role Play Cards- is a method for brainstorming. This method is recommended for highly creative brainstorming sessions. The use of this method eliminates the possibility of having participants be reluctant or ashamed to share their own creative ideas. Each participant is asked to produce ideas having a different identity (e.g., a representative of Academia is asked to brainstorm ideas as a representative from the Private Sector, taking into consideration the corresponding perspective/interest).
Step 2: Screening or feasibility assessment	Focus Group Discussion	See the brief description of this tool in Step 0 of this table.
Step 3: Defining evaluation criteria	Brainstorming	See the brief description of this tool in Step 1 of this table.
	Round Tables	Round Tables constitute a tool for discussion and debate within a group. Participants are asked to contribute to the discussion upon an agreed topic, having equal rights to participate.
	World Café	World Café is an engagement method for various target groups. It is a simple method where all participants can talk upon a topic, expressing their own views and/or concerns. It is developed upon the principle that participants can work collaboratively, regardless their identity or background.
Step 4: Scoring or assessment of options	Expert Panels	Expert Panels is a method that is used when expert knowledge is required. The experts are asked to respond to the (so far) produced results of a group, evaluating them and providing input and or/opinion upon them.
	Focus Group Discussion	See the brief description of this tool in Step 0 of this table.
Step 5: Weighting of evaluation criteria	Focus Group Discussion (with experts' participation)	See the brief description of this tool in Step 0 of this table.
Step 6: Ranking and prioritization of options	Prioritization	Prioritization is a method, with which a group of participants is asked to prioritize previously selected options/suggestion, based on their level of urgency and level of importance. Participants must find consensus on the final result and ranking of their final selection of options/suggestions.
	Focus Group Discussion	See the brief description of this tool in Step 0 of this table.

8.6.2. Selecting tools and methods

It is important to contextualize the MCA process, and consequently every step, for the case at hand. Therefore, it is essential to take into consideration a series of factors that determine the appropriateness of an engagement tool or method. To begin with, it is important to consider the intended input that is aimed to be gained from the stakeholders' engagement. The engagement tools and methods that are about to be chosen for each MCA step need to contribute to the overall desired outcome.

For the SCORE MCA process, three types of stakeholder engagement were identified, including in some cases experts' involvement:

- Ideation, where stakeholders are asked to come up with ideas for adaptation options (see Step 1).
- Co-decision, where stakeholders jointly discuss and agree on the results for specific steps of the MCA process (see Steps 2, 3, 5 and 6).

- Experts' consultation, where experts are asked to join and provide their inputs (see Step 4).

Along with the intended output to be gained from the stakeholders' engagement, it is important to take also into consideration the temporal dimension of the MCA process. The time span available for each of the engagement tools or methods should be in line with the overall timeline of the MCA process. Therefore, for each of the MCA steps, an engagement tool or method should be selected that can be facilitated within a maximum of half a day workshop with the stakeholders.

Another determining factor when selecting engagement tools/methods is the number of the involved stakeholders to the MCA process. There is a possibility of ending up with different sizes of stakeholders' groups (that can range from small to medium or large groups). Different size of stakeholders' groups may require different types of tools/methods. Therefore, it is important to select engagement tools or methods that can be successfully facilitated with the size of the stakeholders' group that is involved in the MCA process.

Table 11 below presents an overview of the engagement tools and methods, based on the type of the stakeholder engagement, including the size of the stakeholders' groups to be engaged as well as the duration of their facilitation.

Table 11: Overview of stakeholder engagement tools and methods based on the type of engagement

Type of engagement	Tool name	Size of stakeholders' group	Duration
Ideation	Brainstorming	Small, Medium, or Large	1-2 hours
	Rolestorming (Role Play Cards)	Small, Medium, or Large	1 hour/topic
	Idea Dashboard	Small and Medium (max 15)	30-40 minutes/round
	Brainwriting	Small (min 4, max 6)	30 minutes/round and 1-2 hour for group reflection and final selection
Co-decision	Focus Group Discussion	Small, Medium and Large	2-3 hours
	Round Tables	Small, Medium and Large	1-2 hour/round table and 1-2 hour for group reflection and final selection
	World café Method	Small, Medium and Large	20 minutes/round (category) and 1-2h for group reflection and final selection
	Prioritization	Small, Medium and Large	2-3 hours
Experts' consultation	Expert Panels	As required	As required

8.7. Step-by-step Guidelines for MCA

This section provides a list of instructions (and examples) as well as templates for the application of the MCA. An integrated Microsoft excel-based tool, which supports the MCA process, can be developed for actual application. Further, Annex 1 outlines the moderation guidelines for the stakeholder engagement tools and methods that can be used in the MCA process.

Step 0. Understanding the local adaptation context

In this step, key questions for Focus Group Discussion among stakeholders include the following: What were/are the previous, current, and future plans and strategies for climate change adaptation, including EbAs? What are the available ecosystems and ecosystem services provided in the area? What are the main hazards and impacts, and where are they spatially located? What have been the results of vulnerability assessments, if available? What

objectives can be set for the MCA process, and what can be the desired outputs and results? Which main stakeholders will be involved in each step of the MCA process?

Step 1. Identifying a list of preliminary options

As a starting point, a database of EbAs options will be provided for this step in the MCA process. This database includes descriptions of EbAs options and other information that would serve as reference for stakeholders.

Specifically, this involves the following sub-steps:

1. Using brainstorming, idea dashboard, brainwriting, or rolestorming, etc. as tools and methods for engaging stakeholders, a list of preliminary options will be identified. Stakeholders are not limited to the EbAs options mentioned in the database as this step requires coming up with (new) ideas.
2. Indicate the type of hazards, potential locations, and the land use types that will be addressed by the EbAs options in the CCLL. If necessary, provide additional information for each EbAs option.

Table 12: Example for Step 1: Identifying a list of preliminary options

No.	EbA options	Description (Source: Ruangpan et al., 2021)	Type of hazard(s) addressed	Potential location(s) of the EbA option	Land use type(s) covered
1	Afforestation	Afforestation is the process of planting trees or sowing seeds in areas that have ever been forested to create a forest	Flooding	Rural area	Mountainous area
2	Reforestation	Reforestation is the restoration of forests in areas where forests were removed or destroyed	Flooding	Rural area	Mountainous area
3	Wetland restoration	A wetland is an area of marsh, fern, peatland or water	Coastal flooding, inland flooding	Peri-urban area	Coastal area
4	Flood plain enlargement/restoration	The floodplain can be enlarged by lowering the level and/or increasing the width of the flood plain area	Coastal flooding, inland flooding	Peri-urban area	Floodplain
5	Retention ponds	Retention ponds are natural depressions designed with additional storage capacity to attenuate surface runoff during rainfall events	Coastal flooding, inland flooding	Urban area	Coastal area

Step 2. Screening or feasibility assessment

Narrow down the options identified in Step 1. This task will screen out adaptation actions that may not be viable to implement and bring forward alternative adaptation actions for a more detailed assessment.

Specifically, this involves the following sub-steps.

- o Evaluate the feasibility of the EbAs options using the following criteria (UN HABITAT, 2014):
 - i. Stakeholder acceptability: Would local stakeholders accept this option?
 - ii. Technical feasibility: Will the necessary designs, skills, competencies, and maintenance support be available for this option?

- iii. Ease of implementation: Can it be implemented at the local government level, or does it depend upon state/provincial or national support?
- iv. Financial feasibility: Is it a financially realistic option? Does the city have funds or potential access to funds to cover the costs?
 - o Assign a score for each of the feasibility criteria using the following scale: low (1), very low (2), medium (3), high (4), and very high (5). If necessary, provide additional feasibility criteria (see Table 13).
 - o Focus Group Discussions can allow the stakeholders to evaluate the options. In case of large stakeholders' groups, sub-groups can also be created, allowing at the end an overall reflection and comparison of the results.
 - o Observe how the scores for each option add up, as well as how the options are ranked overall.
 - o Based on the results of this step, the top ranked options can be brought forward for further assessment.

Table 13: Sample template for Step 2: Screening or feasibility assessment: Scoring

No.	EbA options	Stakeholder acceptability	Technical feasibility	Ease of Implementation	Financial Feasibility	Total	Ranking
1	Afforestation	5	5	5	5	20	1
2	Reforestation	5	4	4	4	17	2
3	Wetland restoration	5	4	4	3	16	2
4	Flood plain enlargement/restoration	3	3	3	2	11	4
5	Retention ponds	4	4	4	3	15	3

Step 3. Defining evaluation criteria

To guide the process, a database of evaluation criteria is provided for this step of the MCA process. This database includes descriptions of evaluation criteria and other information that would serve as reference for stakeholders. As the focus is on EbAs, this includes criteria related to ecosystem service provision.

Specifically, this involves the following sub-steps.

- a. Stakeholders can examine the database of possible evaluation criteria and/or associated indicators and select which ones to use for this step. Stakeholders can add other criteria, if necessary.
- b. Brainstorming, round tables, or world café sessions can be utilized to engage stakeholders on this step.
- c. The unit of measurement, as well as the direction of preference (min-max), for each criterion are provided in the database. Stakeholders can choose quantitative and/or qualitative scales for the units of measurement. Quantitative measurements, such as costs in euros or geographical area of coverage in terms of square meters, can be expressed in scales. Qualitative scales, on the other hand, can be "1 to 10" or "1 to 5" where 1 indicates very low performance and 10 or 5 shows very high performance.

- d. For environmental or social criteria, the direction of preference should be maximum as reaping the maximum benefits derived from the adaptation action is ideal. However, for economic criteria, the direction of preference should be minimum as the least cost adaptation option is better.

Table 14: Sample template for Step 3: Defining evaluation criteria

No.	Criteria / Indicator	Unit of Measurement	Min-Max
1	Flood risk reduction	1-5	Max
2	Increase habitat area (quantity)	1-5	Max
3	Habitat provision and distribution (quality)	1-5	Max

Step 4. Scoring or assessment of options

For this step, expert judgement is required for assigning scores to each of the previously selected options, against the evaluation criteria identified in Step 2.

Specifically, this involves the following sub-steps.

- The experts participating in this MCA step are suggested to be organized in a panel, evaluating the impact (social, environmental, economic, etc.) of the selected options. The preparation for the scoring or assessment of options can be done beforehand.
- After the expert panel has assigned scores to the options, it is important to ensure the consensus of the engaged stakeholders. It is, therefore, suggested to have a joint Focus Group Discussion, where experts will present their results to stakeholders.
- To minimize ambiguity and subjectivity, scoring should be based on a clearly understood and agreed upon scale. In this regard, a smaller scoring scale is easier to use and is less subjective than a larger scale (for instance, values of 55 to 80 could denote an important impact on a scale of 0 to 100, where 2 is the only value available on a scale of 1 to 3). The importance of a smaller scale is even greater when the analysis is conducted in a participatory manner.
- If the selected criteria do not all use the same scoring scale, one must standardize the values in order to be able to compare the scores. Standardization can be done on a 0 to 1 or to a 0 to 100 scale using the min-max standardization technique which can be done automatically using a Microsoft Excel document.
- Verify that all the criteria scores are in the same direction (i.e., that higher numbers represent a positive outcome and lower numbers represent less positive or negative outcomes or vice versa). For instance, when scoring for costs and benefits one must ensure that the action with the greatest benefits receives the highest positive score, while the option with the greatest costs receives the lowest score (as this is a negative attribute). All the scoring scales must be in the same direction (from negative to positive values).

Table 15: Sample template for Step 4: Scoring or assessment of options

No.	EbA options	Flood risk reduction	Increase habitat area (quantity)	Habitat provision and distribution (quality)	Initial Scoring (Average)	Initial Ranking
1	Afforestation	2	3	5	3	5
2	Reforestation	3	3	5	4	3
3	Wetland restoration	3	4	4	4	3

No.	EbA options	Flood risk reduction	Increase habitat area (quantity)	Habitat provision and distribution (quality)	Initial Scoring (Average)	Initial Ranking
4	Floodplain enlargement/restoration	5	5	5	5	1
5	Retention ponds	4	4	4	4	2

Source: The scores of EBA options against the evaluation criteria have been adapted from Ruangpan et al. (2021).

Step 5. Weighting of evaluation criteria

In this step, the group undertaking the analysis, in accordance with experts and stakeholders, must decide if any of the criteria should be given a higher or lower weight with respect to the others. Weighting of criteria should be at the heart of group discussions, as it may change the ranking of adaptation actions.

Specifically, this involves the following sub-steps.

- Focus Group Discussions can be carried out to allocate weights to the selected evaluation criteria by the stakeholders. However, in case of large stakeholders' groups, sub-groups can also be created, allowing a subsequent overall reflection and comparison of the results by all participants.
- Experts are also suggested to be engaged in this step, joining the Focus Group Discussions. In case of more than one discussion groups, it is suggested to ensure the optimal balance among stakeholders and experts for each of the sub-groups.
- If the ranking of adaptation actions changes as a result of modifying the criteria weights, the groups should analyse and discuss the results to ensure that everyone agrees on certain weights as factors of relative importance and as inputs in the final ranking of adaptation options.

Table 16: Sample template for Step 5: Weighting of evaluation criteria

No.	EbA options	Flood risk reduction	Increase habitat area (quantity)	Habitat provision and distribution (quality)	Total Weight
		50%	25%	25%	100%

Step 6. Ranking and prioritization of options

The final ranking of the options can be calculated by multiplying the weights of the evaluation criteria with the score for each option. This can be done automatically using a Microsoft Excel document.

Specifically, this involves the following sub-steps.

- For this final step of the MCA, stakeholders are invited to discuss the final ranking. Getting consensus from all the stakeholders regarding this ranking might prove challenging.
- It is, therefore, suggested to use a visual prioritization technique, in order to allow the stakeholders to express their preference regarding the finally ranked adaptation actions. By using this technique and combining it with a Focus Group Discussion setting (similar to the previous step), stakeholders can evaluate the final ranking.

Table 17: Sample template for Step 6: Ranking and prioritization of options

No.	EbA options	Flood risk reduction	Increase habitat area (quantity)	Habitat provision and distribution (quality)	Final Scoring	Final Ranking
		50%	25%	25%		
1	Afforestation	$0,5 * 2 = 1$	$0,25 * 3 = 0,75$	$0,25 * 5 = 1,25$	3	4
2	Reforestation	$0,5 * 3 = 1,5$	$0,25 * 3 = 0,75$	$0,25 * 5 = 1,25$	3,5	3
3	Wetland restoration	$0,5 * 3 = 1,5$	$0,25 * 4 = 1$	$0,25 * 4 = 1$	3,5	3
4	Floodplain enlargement/restoration	$0,5 * 5 = 2,5$	$0,25 * 5 = 0,25$	$0,25 * 5 = 1,25$	5	1
5	Retention ponds	$0,5 * 4 = 2$	$0,25 * 4 = 1$	$0,25 * 4 = 1$	4	2

Step 7. Sensitivity analysis

A sensitivity analysis will be carried out by the research team without the involvement of stakeholders. This step entails adjusting input variables to understand the effect on the overall scoring and ranking. The results of the MCA process will be validated by the stakeholders and experts. Overall, MCA is an iterative process wherein steps can be revisited and adjusted before making a final decision or recommendation.

9. COST-BENEFIT ANALYSIS WITHIN SCORE'S COASTAL CITY LIVING LABS

The CBA methodology is designed to help decision-makers prioritise adaptation interventions by comparing and identifying the optimal EbA from a cost-effective and social perspective. Incorporating environmental perspectives and a social discount rate, makes possible to bring evidence on how EbA contribute to the provision of ecosystem services by considering ecosystem services provision as co-benefits. The following sections contextualize the CBA approach and present the Net Present Value (NPV) methodology. There are then presented methods to identify costs and benefits, there are defined the discount rates, and determined the temporal horizon, and examples of valuation methods, data requirements, and data sources are provided. Sensitivity analysis to adjust and validate the model closes the chapter.

9.3. Introduction

9.3.1.1. The CBA approach

To assess the potential economic and social costs and benefits of EbA as described in previous sections, a cost benefit analysis (CBA) approach is used. The CBA approach involves estimating the monetary, non-monetary and wider macroeconomic costs and benefits that are important. The CBA is a widely used analytical tool and extended

for the evaluation of investment decisions. The purpose of this tool is to generate a more efficient allocation of resources in order to demonstrate the benefits of the analysed interventions generated for the society.

In the case of planning for climate change adaptation, CBA provides a straightforward tool to quantify the impacts of an array of climate change projections during the analysis of a project. Rainfall scenarios, sea level rise, temperature increases, flooding and the frequency of catastrophic weather events can all be addressed by the analysis to test whether a proposed investment can withstand the test of time when the climate is changing (USAID Adapt Asia-Pacific, 2016).

Figure 3: Example of Cost-benefit approach

9.3.1.2. Concepts, advantages, and limitations

Following the Guide to Cost-Benefit Analysis of Investment projects of 2014, the analytical framework of this tool refers to several **underlying concepts** that need to be considered:

- **Opportunity cost.** This can be defined as the potential gain from the best forgone alternative, when a choice needs to be made between alternatives that are mutually excluded.
- **Long-term perspective.** Depending on the sector and the characteristics of the intervention, a specific time outlook needs to be established. During the established timeframe, what will be required is a proper forecasting of future costs and benefits, and their conversion to present values through the adoption of a specific discount rate.
- **Calculation of indicators of economic performance expressed in monetary terms.** For the CBA, it is required to provide a monetary value to all the benefits and costs generated by the intervention. Later, these values need to be discounted and added so that the net total benefit can be calculated. When doing the calculation, the financial performance of the intervention can be evaluated, and the Economic Net Present Value (ENPV) is calculated. This formula provides the monetary values of the effects of the interventions allowing comparability between competing ideas.
- **Microeconomic approach.** This refers to the microeconomic nature of the CBA when assessing expected welfare changes, giving as a result the impact of the EBA intervention for society as a whole.
- **Incremental approach.** A CBA can be defined as a counterfactual analysis between a baseline scenario without the intervention and a scenario with the intervention. The counterfactual scenario is defined as what would happen if the intervention would not be implemented. For this scenario to be generated, projections of all cash flows need to be estimated for each year of the intervention lifetime.

This cash flow projections need to consider all the investment, including financial and economic costs and benefits from the project.

Advantages

Overall, the CBA provides an overview of the benefits and costs of actions that can be monetized. More specific **advantages** generated by the CBA analysis are the following:

1. The decision rules that are used by the analysis are standardized and largely known.
2. It generates non-prescriptive information in a standard format that can be useful for decision makers and stakeholders.
3. The method is flexible and adaptable enough to consider income distributional effects, intergenerational trade-offs, financial efficiency, and the effects generated by externalities.
4. A CBA analysis can also be extended to include a stakeholder analysis showing the project's capacities, long term impacts and affected parties.
5. Finally, the CBA analysis has the capacity to reduce the information regarding the impact of an environmental project to a single number: a benefit/cost ratio, an internal rate of return or an NPV. This allows to have a simple and efficient decision-making process or comparison between projects.

Limitations

On the other hand, there are some limitations regarding this methodology, especially, when applying it to climate change adaptation measures. The **main limitations** are:

1. The lack of capacity when trying to economically assess all benefits.
2. The complexity when selecting an appropriate discount rate to determine the present value of future costs and benefits.
3. The underlying limitation is the intangible aspect of environmental aspects.
4. Potential manipulation of the process by political interests and pressure groups which might bring forward their own agendas as to what needs to be valued or not.

In a more theoretical and abstract level, CBA is based on the assumption that all human actions are “instrumental” (or “utilitarian”), i.e. they are means to achieve an end. Hence, any action (and project) is assessed only in relation to its results. Benefits that accrue from the implementation of the action are unimportant. An objection can be raised, however, that not all human actions are instrumental, and that some actions can be defined by different motivations than maximizing end benefits. These actions might be defined as expressive, as there is a tendency to act according to one's beliefs or moral values, regardless of benefits and costs. There might be defined as a tendency toward autonomy, ability of an individual to take their own decisions for themselves. Or they might be defined by altruism, a tendency to do things for the benefit of others (including the future generations). CBA (as any other “instrumental” utilitarian method) simply fails to take the above motivations into account.

9.3.1.3. Seven stages for implementing a cost-benefit analysis

Much information has been written on the economics of climate change adaptation, and even more on the economic analysis of costs and benefits. This report adds to the existing literature by sharing one practical approach to tackling the task of quantifying the costs and benefits of climate change adaptation actions. The

proposed CBA methodology breaks the analysis down into the following seven steps.

Figure 4: Seven stages for implementing a cost-benefit analysis

Source: Adapted from USAID Adapt Asia-Pacific, 2016.

5.2. Definition of the CBA framework and CCLL objectives

The first stage of the implementation of the CBA targets the definition of the CBA framework aligned with the CCLL characteristics. Following the definition given by USAID Adapt Asia-Pacific (2016), a CBA is understood as *“a decision-making tool that helps governments design better policies and implement more effective and equitable projects for long-term sustainable results.”* In this sense, the CBA should be discussed, defined, and agreed among the involved parties in the CCLL so that it is clearly and correctly specified before using it.

One of the main points of the first stage of the CBA implementation is to understand the climate change risks that the CCLL is facing to establish the correct solutions to meet the goals and therefore propose the correct scope for the analysis. Based on the results of the climate change scenarios developed in the SCORE project the objectives of the CBA should be addressed as part of a strategic discussion, so as to establish a sound set of objectives that will facilitate having a solid analytical framework.

Involved parties can be the institutions that lead the analysis (project partners and/or CCLL team) as well as the entities in charge of carrying it (CCLL team and or project partners). Moreover, stakeholders that are not directly involved in the development of the CBA, but are affected by the intervention, should also be involved in the process.

In the context of the SCORE project, the CCLLs main objective is to promote climate adaptation through the implementation of EBAs. Indeed, the CCLLs perceive climate change to be their principal problem, with initial impacts already being felt in commercial buildings, tourism, residential buildings, energy and transport networks or cultural heritage as a consequence of hazards such as sea level rise, flooding, and more frequent and severe climate events (e.g., storms, cyclones, heat waves).

Having defined the CCLLs' main objective, the CBA has the potential to directly contribute to the process of selecting the most appropriate EBA depending on each CCLL context. In detail, the CBA will allow to identify which one of the adaptation measures provides the highest return to society for each euro invested.

As a result of this first stage, the conducted CBA will add valuable information to policy makers about the impacts the adaptation investment policies might have. At this first stage, the CBA assessment will highlight the impacts that investing in the implementation of an EBA might have in the CCLL.

9.4. Understanding the Net Present Value Approach.

When using a CBA analysis there are several ways of quantifying a benefit/cost ratio, an internal rate of return or a NPV. The quantification metric selected for this case is the NPV, as it is the most comprehensive indicator to assess a project from a CBA standpoint.

The NPV of a project can be defined as the **difference between the total social costs and benefits, discounted in the project's time horizon with a specific discount rate**. In other words, the NPV approach estimates the value of the stream of net benefits that are expected to be generated over the temporal horizon, **in this case as a consequence of the implementation of an EbA**. These values are then discounted back to the present accounting period. This provides a single estimate of the capital value of the asset at a given point in time.

Figure 5: Net present value approach within a CBA

The methodology consists of identifying all those cash flows and non-monetary benefits that the asset, in this case the EbA project, is going to generate in the coming years and bring the benefits to current values. That is, the valuation would be represented by the following formula:

$$ENPV = \sum_{t=0}^T \frac{ABS_t}{(1+i)^t}$$

Where:

- ENPV = Economic or social net present value
- ABS_t = Increase in social Benefits (Benefits-Costs). Usually this is considered the cash flow of the

investment.

- i = discount rate
- T = time horizon

When it comes to the application of this methodology to an **environmental intervention/investment there are different aspects that need to be considered**, in terms of the social benefit and to increase the comparability between interventions:

- **Costs and Benefits.** It is relevant to specify which ecosystem variables will be considered when identifying the costs and benefits. All these aspects are widely explained in following sections.
- **Discount rate.** Identification of a proper discount rate considering the characteristics and expected outcome of the intervention/investment.
- **The temporal horizon**, which requires for a definition of a determined period where the social benefits (benefits -costs) are expected to be generated.

9.4. Identifying costs and benefits methods

9.4.1.1. Previous considerations

The proposed CBA methodology assumes a precautionary approach regarding the monetary valuation of nature. This means that the analysis will focus on those ecosystem services that are associated with a direct (e.g., provision of food, support of recreation and tourism activities) or indirect (e.g., carbon sequestration, coastal protection) appointed values that have been frequently considered in the literature. On the contrary, more intangible aspects such as the intrinsic value of ecosystems and species, and cultural ecosystem services cannot be considered.

Many EBA-related benefits are the inverse of climate losses or damages, and so to value both as separate items might result in double-counting. Items may also be expressed in terms of metrics that cannot be compared. That is why standardization is important. Some values may be able to be monetised (such as the value of project costs), others quantified only in physical terms (such as square kilometres of flood-impact zone), and others only qualitatively described (such as improvements in social empowerment and wellbeing or changes in policy and institutional settings). Indeed, this is one of the reasons that a range of different methods and technical approaches are required to value EBA benefits.

9.4.1.2. Environmental impacts in frontrunners CCLL's

Coastal flooding and coastal erosion are some of the main **environmental impacts expected** in the frontrunners CCLLs. The protection that natural habitats provide against flooding or erosion can be assessed following two types of analysis approaches, based on: (1) index-based; or (2) process-based:

- (1) **Index-based approaches** use estimates of exposure and vulnerability (physical and socioeconomic) to calculate an index related to the characteristics of the coastal zone. The index can be calculated under various scenarios or situations, for example using different configurations of natural habitats or environmental conditions, and by comparison, understanding the range of possible impacts and actions. For example, indices have been used on the US coast to determine flood hazard and the protection provided by ecosystems (Arkema et al., 2013), as well as vulnerability to coastal erosion.

- (2) In contrast, **process-based assessments** examine how meteo-oceanographic variables (waves, tides, currents, sea level, wind) influence coastal processes (sediment transport, interaction with structures, inundation) to determine how habitats modify these processes and avoid impacts or damage. This approach includes the physics of the processes and provides quantitative information on the extent or magnitude of the impact in terms of physical metrics such as area inundated or eroded, economic value damaged, etc (Reguero et al., 2013).

Ecosystems can reduce erosion and build sediments, and in some cases maintain or increase the surface elevation of the substrate. Many ecosystems do generate organic and/or mineral sediments such as carbonate sands, and vegetation detritus (e.g., McKee, 2011). By reducing wave energy, they lower water velocities and shear stress near the seabed, reducing erosion and enhancing particulate deposition (de Boer, 2007). Erosion may be further reduced through mechanical protection provided by biofilms, roots, and rhizomes, or through alteration of the mechanical and chemical properties of the substrate (e.g., Murphy & Tolhurst, 2009). The importance of erosion reduction in saltmarshes was recently highlighted in the Gulf of Mexico: rapid erosion occurred where marsh hedge plants had been killed by oiling, but the erosion slowed after the ecosystem's recovery (Silliman et al., 2012). In the same region, oyster reefs are being actively restored along eroding coastlines and have reduced erosion along marsh hedges (Scyphers et al., 2011).

9.4.1.3. Benefits (ecosystem services)

In the current methodological approach, the ecosystem benefits will be considered in terms of a higher provision of ecosystem services with the implementation of the adaptation measure. Several ecosystem services are related to the prevention of a certain damage, thus the theoretical loss of these services results in increased damages and costs. Several standard methods can be used to value the ecosystem services such as the avoided cost method, willingness to pay (WTP), hedonic pricing, market pricing or travel cost methods.

The following Ecosystem Services are four examples of potential main regulation ecosystem services and co-benefits addressed in the CBA. Two of them are related to the risk reduction whilst the other two are an extra asset that EBAs can supply.

- **Risk Reduction**

- **Coastal erosion**

Based on the work of the group of Environmental Hydraulics Institute (IH Cantabria), (Toimil et al., 2018) developed a methodology on the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) risk framework (IPCC, 2014), Coastal erosion risk reduction is an ecosystem service that can be quantified in terms of (1) recreational benefits losses and (2) the value of the net loss of land as detailed in below.

(1) Assess the consequences of erosion risk in terms of **loss of recreational use value per square meter** of beach for each one of the study areas. In brief, the steps are outlined below:

- Evaluation of the space used per beach user.
- Evaluation of the number of hours per year of recreational service, considering the length of the bathing season, the daily hours, and an estimate of the effective rate of use.
- Estimation of the value of recreational use per square meter of beach.

(2) To calculate the net loss value of the coastal erosion, the area lost, and the land use can be multiplied by the cadastral land value per square meter.

- **Flood Risk reduction**

The monetary value of reduced flood risk can be determined **using the avoided cost method**, i.e. using the costs of damage to properties and possessions of flooding (for example, by using Weighted Annual Average Damage (AAD values) as a proxy. In this case, the avoided cost method is based on the principle that the ecosystem restoration can increase the ability of the habitat to store water, resulting in a lower chance of flooding downstream. As a result, subsequent cost-savings occur, from not having to provide compensation for the losses and damages caused. However, to produce a robust estimate of potential avoided losses, the number of homes, businesses and land which would benefit from reduced flood risk needs to be known. This is only possible when considering a particular site of restoration (Dicks, 2020).

Benefits of flood risk reduction include the decrease in damage costs, which can be subdivided in direct costs (repair of buildings and interior damage), costs of business (interruption of companies' activities in the flooded area), and indirect costs outside the flooded area (mainly due to business interruption). Moreover, the potential economic growth due to improved flood defence should be considered in a cost-benefit analysis.

- **Co-benefits to be measured**

Co-benefits are additional positive impacts to the main objective of the project. In this case, apart from the expected risk reduction as the main benefit, it is assumed that there are certain co-benefits related to the ecosystem services provided by the EBAs. Some examples include carbon sequestration and recreational benefits, which can be monetized and included in the cost-benefit analysis of EBAs. These ecosystems services are explained in detail below.

(1) Carbon sequestration:

Quantifying the benefits of carbon sequestration in monetary terms can be done in a simple fashion by multiplying the amount of carbon sequestered or emissions avoided by restored ecosystem, by a price applied to carbon emissions. From the literature and current data sources it is possible to obtain data covering either the carbon emissions released by degraded ecosystems (which could be avoided via restoration) or estimated annual sequestration rates of restored ecosystems (Dicks, 2020). This approach can be distinguished in traded and non-traded carbon prices:

- The traded carbon price reflects the value of carbon emissions traded on the EU Emissions Trading System (ETS). The latter is the international's first major carbon market and works as a 'cap and trade' system, which sets a limit on the use of total greenhouse gas emissions and converts this amount into tradable emission allowances. Hence, the traded carbon price is typically used for appraising policies that affect the level of emissions in sectors covered by the EU ETS.

Trading Economics Carbon Emissions Allowances Prices are sourced from the European Union Emissions Trading System (EU ETS), the world's largest cap and trade greenhouse gas emissions market. Allowances for carbon emissions are first allocated considering EU directives for the maximum amount of greenhouse gases that can be emitted. Allowances for carbon emissions are then auctioned and traded.¹

- There are, however, other mechanisms that can be applied when setting up a carbon price. Some examples:

- **A carbon tax** directly sets a price on carbon by defining an explicit tax rate on GHG emissions or— more commonly— the carbon content of fossil fuels, i.e., a price per tCO₂e. It is different from an ETS in that the emission reduction outcome of a carbon tax is not pre-defined, but the carbon price is.

¹ The daily carbon price can be checked in <https://tradingeconomics.com/commodity/carbon> (09/06/2022).

- **An offset mechanism** designates the GHG emission reductions from project- or program-based activities, which can be sold either domestically or in other countries. Offset programs issue carbon credits according to an accounting protocol and have their own registry. These credits can be used to meet compliance under an international agreement, domestic policies or corporate citizenship objectives related to GHG mitigation.

- **RBCF** is a funding approach where payments are made after pre-defined outputs or outcomes related to managing climate change, such as emission reductions, are delivered and verified. Many RBCF programs aim to purchase verified reductions in GHG emissions while at the same time reduce poverty, improve access to clean energy and offer health and community benefits.

(2) Recreational Benefits:

Restored ecosystems create new recreational benefits, such as areas for walking, enjoying nature and educational visits (considered as cultural ecosystem services). The recreational opportunities created by restoring ecosystems, and the associated opportunities for improved health and well-being, are substantial **non-market benefits** to be included in cost-benefit analysis. It should be noted, however, that some recreational activities might be lost by re-wetting the landscape, including the ability to walk, horse ride or hunt on the land, and the opportunity cost of losing the ability to carry out these activities should also be taken into account.

Various methods are commonly used for valuating recreational benefits. On one side, there are **stated preference techniques** available, such as contingent valuation and choice modelling. These methods assess behaviour in hypothetical markets through a survey-based approach in which it could be derived the willingness to pay (WTP) of individuals for enjoying certain recreational activities. WTP is the maximum price an individual is willing to pay for a product or service. It is typically represented by a price range. While potential customers are likely willing to pay less than this threshold, it is important to understand that, in most cases, they would not pay a higher price. Moreover, **revealed preference techniques** can be applied to this case. Some examples include the travel cost method, which focus on the observation of travel behaviour of users; or the hedonic pricing method, which allows to estimate the economic value of environmental characteristics potentially affecting property prices. Finally, techniques such as the benefit transfer method or meta-analysis allow to apply the results of primary valuation studies in other areas.

- **Co-benefits that are difficult to be included in the CBA**

The EBAs would potentially provide other Ecosystem Services that could be relevant but are either difficult to monetize or are considered to have mainly secondary effects that are partially captured in the measured ones. Whenever there is the possibility to include the economical value of other Ecosystem Services due to data availability, specific studies that have been carried out in the CCLL, or other reasons, and after checking that there is no double counting between them, these co-benefits should be also taken into account as a benefit in the CBA.

Some of the Ecosystem Services that are considered as co-benefits and that could be measured but show a special difficulty to do so are the following:

- Air pollution removal.
- Biodiversity.
- Improved water quality.
- Temperature regulation and cooling effect.
- Employment and economic opportunities of restoration.
- Cultural ecosystem services.

9.4.1.4. Costs

- **Initial investment:** It refers to the upfront costs required to initiate the implementation of the EBA. These costs include expenses for plantation and revegetation, the cost of erecting fences, the cost of the required machinery, the cost of finance incurred by borrowing to pay for the initial investment.
- **Maintenance costs:** it refers to the recurring costs of monitoring and managing the implemented EBA. These costs include the expense for the maintenance, monitoring of the EBA, wages paid to employees, and the opportunity cost of income.
- **Financial costs:** In case that there is a loan for the implementation of the solution, the future financial costs that may arise to pay back the debt should be considered.

9.5. Defining the discount rate

Selecting an appropriate discount rate is crucial for cost–benefit analysis since it directly impacts the resource allocation. Considering that the investment projects that will be analysed using the CBA methodology have a strong environmental, social and health impact component, models such as the Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) or Weighted Average Cost of Capital (WACC) have been discarded. These models have proven to be useful in investment projects or market transactions with a strong economic or financial component. However, they are not capable of properly addressing some of the key factors, such as the mentioned environmental, social and health impacts, to consider in investment projects such as EBAs. Especially when it comes to the long-term nature of the benefits of these solutions and their intergenerational responsibility. In these cases, the use of these methodologies to determine the discount rates could give rise to errors and not realistic valuations. Therefore, it could end up in a selection of projects that does not prioritize the maximum benefit for the society.

For that reason, **the CBA methodology advocates for the use of the Social Discount Rate (SDR) when trying to take the value of future benefits and costs to the present accounting period.** When it comes to the determination of the SDR, different approaches and methodologies have been developed in the literature. While there is no clear general consensus, it seems that the most popular approaches are the social rate of return on private investments (SRRI) and the social rate of time preference (SRTP) (European Commission, 2014). SRRI is based on the concept that the return of a public investment should be the same as that of a private investment, reasoning those public investments will always be replacing the private ones. This reasoning leads to looking at market discount rates that are too high (Barrett et al., 2000). Market rates generally have risk premiums associated that try to compensate for the risks assumed in the investment. However, from a societal or government perspective, the risk assumed is lower since there is the capacity to exploit the risk pooling. Furthermore, market discount rates such as CAPM or WACC are obtained from the behaviour of different assets in the market, which is strongly conditioned by volatility or in many cases can be affected by bubbles and overvalued assets.

Thus, a SDR based on SRTP approach is considered the most appropriate when it comes to the valuation of EBAs since it considers not only the welfare of current or medium-term generations but also the future generations. Basically, the SRTP approach tries to determine the discount rate that represents the willingness of the society to renounce a current unit of consumption for more future consumption (Zhuang et al., 2007). There are two main ways of estimating the SDR with the SRTP approach: using governments' bond's return rates or applying the Ramsey growth model (Ramsey, 1928), which is represented by the following formula:

$$\text{SRTP} = p + e \cdot g$$

Where:

p = utility discount rate

e = absolute value of the elasticity of marginal utility of consumption (income)

g = average rate of growth of per capita real consumption (income)

The utility discount rate, or p , tries to reflect the time preference or individuals' impatience and risk of not being alive in the future. When it comes to the second part of the formula ($e * g$), it reflects the fact that people will be less willing to save in the current period to obtain more in the future, assuming that consumption will grow and consequently the marginal utility will decrease. Even within the SRTP approach, the consensus is not clear when trying to define an SDR. The main reason is because measuring its components is not something objective and depending on people's criteria and ethical concepts, it may vary significantly. Nevertheless, some of the literature that has tried to measure or set up a SDR for Europe following the SRTP approach have concluded that it should be close to 3%. The Green Book published by the HM Treasury (2018) sets out a SDR of 3.5% and Evans & Sezer (2005) found that European SDR lies between 3% and 5.5% depending on the country. Even in the US, Moore et al. (2013) it is defined at 3.5%. However, some literature state that it is unethical to use a positive SDR mainly because of an intergenerational responsibility matter. From a philosophical or conceptual perspective, critics have resalted the fact that a positive interest rate may encourage current generations' interests, overriding those of future generations. Moreover, environment-based criticism to positive discount rates has been focused on the intergenerational responsibility (OXERA, 2002).

From a theoretical perspective and to gather the differences that may exist among different territories, trying to implement the SRTP formula based on Ramsey growth model would be the optimal solution. However, it is not an easy and fully objective formula and requires having access to data and expert knowledge on the field. Thus, some of the CCLs might be limited on its implementation. Given the reasonable limitations, when applying the SRTP is not possible, using two different discount rates is recommended. **Based on the literature review and research carried out in occidental countries, one of the discount rates should be close to 0.5% and the other one closer to 5.5%.**

9.6. Determination of the temporal horizon

In some cases, the temporal horizon determines the technical or physical life of a project or asset. In the case of EBAs, the temporal horizon defines the time period over which the costs and benefits of the investment project will be summed up to check whether or not the project is successful. Defining a time horizon that covers comprehensively the lifetime of the intervention is key when applying the CBA methodology to evaluate EBAs. As in the case of the discount factor, there are not established rules around which temporal horizon should be used, not even within traditional infrastructure investment projects. However, when trying to determine the period that will be evaluated, the uncertainty and the approach to discounting are usually key aspects to take into consideration. In the case of high discount rates, long temporal horizons are not effective because future effects will not have noticeable impact when discounting them to actual value (Cahill & O'connell, 2018).

In solutions with an environmental component like the EBAs, the initial capital expenditure and maintenance costs will occur since the first year of application of the solution but some of the benefits will not flourish until a considerable amount of time is passed. For that reason, the literature advocates for the use of long temporal horizons when evaluating these kinds of solutions. The World Health Organisation (WHO) considers reasonable to use of a temporal horizon of 100 years to be able to gather the health improvements derived from air pollution reduction (Hutton et al., 2006). The IPCC also considers that the long-term impacts of mitigation projects on greenhouse gases last for centuries. Some of the CBAs carried out to evaluate EBAs in different countries also

consider long temporal horizons that usually range between 50-100 years (Federal Republic of Germany, 2017). Therefore, **it would be suitable to consider long temporal horizons that range between 50-100 years**, depending on the forecasting capacity and data availability.

Regarding the defined climate change scenarios and the expected flooding impacts that are going to be measured, the concept of return period is relevant. The return period is explained as the probability climatic events such as floods, windstorms or tornadoes will occur. Calculating the inverse of the return period, generally expressed as a percentage (%), gives the estimated time interval between the events of a similar intensity or magnitude. For example, if the return period for floodings is 100 years, the probability of a flood event to occur in one year is 1/100, or 1% in any one year. However, it is important to consider that this does not mean that if a flood occurs one year, then the next will occur in one hundred years; instead, it means that, in any given year, there is a 1% chance a flood will happen, despite when the last flooding event was. **These temporal horizons can be aligned with the expressed range between 50-100 years.**

9.7. Measuring and valuing costs and benefits: valuation methods, data required and data sources

Once the previous steps are done, the CBA analysis can be developed by applying the (2) Net Present Value methodology under the determined characteristics regarding the (1) pursued goals, (3) costs/benefits, (4) discounts rate, and the (5) temporal horizon.

To measure the costs and benefits, it is recommended to build up a summary chart addressing the following information to set the conditions under which the CBA is going to be performed and calculated.

The summary chart will help to structure the needs to carry out the CBA analysis while orienting what type of information is needed and where the information could be gathered. As the chart is fulfilled and the discount rates and time horizon are established, the CBA tool can be applied throughout Net Present Value Approach.

Table 18: Example of valuation method, data required and source of the data.

Cost/Benefit	Valuation Method	Data required	Source of Data
Cost 1. Initial investment	Use quotations from contractors to estimate the contract amount, including capital and labour costs.	Contract amount for project period.	Contract amount for project period.
Cost 2. Maintenance cost	Use current market price data or figures from previous projects.	Use current market price data or figures from previous projects.	Record of administrative expenses from previous projects or an estimation based on market prices.
Cost 3. Financial costs	In case that there is indebtedness for the implementation of the solution, the future financial costs that may arise in order to pay back the debt.	Financial interests.	Data provided by the loan entity.

Cost/Benefit	Valuation Method	Data required	Source of Data
Benefit 1. Coastal erosion	Estimate expected average value of losses by multiplying (historical disaster loss assessment data) x (future frequency of flash foods as estimated by climate predictions). Decrease in losses due to the new EBA can be estimated by engineers.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Euro value of losses incurred by various sectors during previous floods. - Number of floods. - Climate predictions for likelihood of floods. - Euro value of decreased damage. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Disaster loss assessment report. - Climate predictions.
Benefit 2. Flood risk	Estimate expected average value of losses by multiplying (historical disaster loss assessment data) x (future frequency of flash foods as estimated by climate predictions). Decrease in losses due to the new EBA can be estimated by engineers.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Euro value of losses incurred by various sectors during previous floods. - Number of floods. - Climate predictions for likelihood of floods. - Euro value of decreased damage. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Disaster loss assessment report. - Climate predictions.
Benefit 3. Carbon sequestration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The traded carbon price reflects the value of carbon emissions traded on the EU Emissions Trading System (ETS). - The non-traded carbon price is based on estimates of the abatement costs incurred to meet the emissions reduction targets set in Climate Change regulations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - tCO₂/year absorption capacity by the EBA. - The traded carbon price. - The non-traded carbon price. 	Bibliography.
Benefit 4. Recreational benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Revealed preference techniques such as the Travel Cost Method. - State preference techniques such as contingent valuation and choice modelling. - Benefit-transfer method, and meta-analysis. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Amount of money people are willing to pay. - The costs of the travel to visit the place. 	Surveys and/or bibliography.

9.8. Making a sensitivity analysis. Adjust and validation of the CBA model

The seventh and last stage of the guideline concerns conducting a sensitivity analysis. A sensitivity analysis seeks to determine if an analysis provides consistent results, even when there is uncertainty about some of the parameters (USAID Adapt Asia-Pacific, 2016). When calculating an activity's benefits and costs, there might be uncertainty about their origin or magnitude. For example, in the context of climate change, the effect of a water harvesting project on water supply may be unclear as, over time, rainfall might change. Indeed, there is a need to check the reliability of the obtained results. To verify if the conclusions of the CBA are robust and can be used for decision-making, a sensitivity analysis should be conducted for those parameters which are uncertain. In the context of climate change, conducting a sensitivity analysis is seen as useful, especially as the prediction of the future climate is uncertain.

In detail, experts consider a sensitivity analysis to be a practical and useful tool that can be used to integrate the

potential impacts of climate change in the CBA and to assess the benefits of the implemented adaptation actions under the full range of climate scenarios. Fundamentally, a robust NPV will indicate that the adaptation project would be a beneficial investment for society even after the sensitivity analysis.

Hence, during this last stage, the CCLL should brainstorm and list those parameters used to quantify the costs and benefits that entail a significant amount of uncertainty. The uncertainty of those items can be identified as values that cannot be absolutely known or have the potential to greatly fluctuate in the future (e.g., the likelihood of an extreme climate event). Once the brainstorming exercise is complete, the NPV calculations can be tested to check whether the results of the CBA are sensitive to the uncertainty of the parameters.

A variety of options can be found to check the sensitivity of the CBA results to changes in parameters. In a straightforward way, this test could involve inserting the upper and lower of the range for each uncertain parameter into the NPV equation. It **could also include comparison with other types of adaptation approaches (e.g., hard-engineering)**. In doing so, the results will fluctuate. Depending on the size of that fluctuation, the sensitivity of the CBA results in relation to the uncertainty of a particular parameter can be assessed.

Figure 6: Robustness of the CBA.

Source: USAID Adapt Asia-Pacific (2016).

10.FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

MCA and CBA assessment methods presented in this report integrate the methodological framework to assess EbA interventions in SCORE's CCLLs. This report needs to be understood as a living document to be further detailed as both methodologies will have to be adapted to the specificities of the area of analysis. The ten CCLLs considered in the SCORE project vary, among other aspects, in terms of the location and scale of the study area, the main hazards and sectoral impacts that need to be addressed, and in terms of their current status of EbA implementation. The latter means that some CCLLs have already implemented or planned EbA solutions that could be analysed from a socioeconomic perspective, while others still need to promote a discussion in which potential new EbA can be addressed within the scope of SCORE. Therefore, when putting into practice the socioeconomic assessments foreseen in tasks 7.3 and 7.4, some methodological aspects will have to be adapted according to the local context. This could be the case for the definition of the area of analysis, the pool of EbAs to consider in the MCA, determining the most appropriate engagement tools for each group of stakeholders, or the selection of ESS to be included as co-benefits within the CBA approach.

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APPENDIX 1

Moderation guidelines for the stakeholder engagement tools and methods of the MCA process.

Table 1: Moderation of engagement tools and methods for Step 0: Understanding the local adaptation context.

Moderation of engagement tools methods	
Focus Group Discussion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Arrange the setting for the participants, based on the size of the group, so that can all see each other during the discussion. • In case of large group of participants, divide the group into sub-groups, and assign one moderator per sub-group to lead the discussion. • Prepare beforehand the following materials: whiteboard(s) or A0 poster(s), sticky notes, markers. • List the questions that participants will have to give input for this step. • Allow/ask all participants to provide their perspective. • Keep track on the timing, ensuring that all the predefined questions will be answered. • In case of sub-groups, allow time at the end (approx. 1 hour) for comparing reflecting upon and comparing the results. • Make sure that you get consensus among participants for the findings, before moving to the next step.

Table 2: Moderation of engagement tools and methods for Step 1: Identifying a list of preliminary options.

Moderation of engagement tools methods	
Brainstorming	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Moderate the session, encouraging participants to develop their ideas, writing their selection of EbAs from the database, or their own ideas, on sticky notes, collecting them all in whiteboards. • Moderate the braistorming session, encouraging all the stakeholders to participate. • Encourage participants to come up also with their own ideas, outside the database. • Keep track on the time, ensuring that 1 hour is allocated for all the topics (climate hazards/impacts). • In case of large group of participants, divide the group into sub-groups, assign one moderator per sub-group to lead the discussion and adjust the time accordingly. Allow at least 30 min at the end for final reflection and consensus on the findings.

Moderation of engagement tools methods

Idea Dashboard		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Ask participants to write down in the dashboard their selection of EbAs, either from the database or their own suggestions. ○ Moderate the session, encouraging the participants to elaborate on their ideas, and discussing them with the other participants. ○ Ask participants specific questions on their selected options, such as “What is the option you selected?”, “How could this option work for the CCLL?”, “Why do you think this option should be selected among the others?”, “What would be the benefits of this option?”. ● Ask participants to provide answers to the questions of the previous step. Wrap up the answers and the final results and ask participants to reflect on them. ● Summarize the final ideas on a new dashboard, and ensure that you get consensus on the final results from all the stakeholders.
Brainwriting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Arrange the setting for the participants, based on the size of the group. ● Provide the participants the database of EbAs in printed or digital version for the session. ● Prepare beforehand the following materials: whiteboard(s) or A0 poster(s), sticky notes, markers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Provide participants sticky notes to write their selections. ● Ask participants to write individually 3 EbA options of their preference per topic on paper: 5min. ● After the first 5 min round, ask participants to pass their papers to the rest of the group (clockwise). ● Repeat the procedure for 6 rounds in total. ● Once all the rounds are finished, gather the selections of the EbA options per topic, excluding any duplicates. ● Ask participant to reflect upon the gathered selections per topic, keeping the options for which there is consensus among all the participants. <p>*This tool can be facilitated also in a 4-3-2 format (4 rounds - 3 minutes per round - 2 ideas per round).</p>

Moderation of engagement tools methods	
Rolestorming	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prepare beforehand stakeholder identity cards for the different types of stakeholders that are involved (but also relevant) for the MCA. Include in the identify cards: Sector represented, Position, Relevance to the CLL, etc. • Ask the participants to choose an identity different from their own. Alternatively, randomly allocate the identities to the participants, or allow them to choose themselves. • It is possible that you may end up with more than one representative from each sector. You need to make sure that everyone has a different identity from their own for the session. • Follow the procedure of the brainstorming, as described above. • In case of large group of participants, divide the group into sub-groups, assign one moderator per sub-group to lead the discussion and adjust the time accordingly. Allow at least 30 min at the end for final reflection and consensus on the findings.

Table 3: Moderation of engagement tools and methods Step 2: Screening or feasibility assessment.

Moderation of engagement tools methods	
Focus Group Discussion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Arrange the setting for the participants, based on the size of the group, so that can all see each other during the discussion. ○ In case of large group of participants, divide the group into sub-groups, and assign one moderator per sub-group to lead the discussion. ○ Prepare beforehand the template of the feasibility matrix (see Table 12 of the main document). ○ Ask participants to discuss upon the assessment criteria of the matrix, one by one, and assign scores to them. ○ Allow/ask all participants to provide their input for all the criteria. ○ Keep track on the timing, ensuring that the matrix will be filled out on time. ○ Allow time for the participants to observe and discussed the assigned scores and the overall ranking of the EbA options (at least 30 min). ○ In case of sub-groups, allow time at the end (approx. 1 hour) for comparing the matrices reflecting upon and comparing the results. ○ Make sure that you get consensus among participants for the findings, ending up with one matrix, before moving to the next step.

Table 4: Moderation of engagement tools and methods for Step 3: Defining evaluation criteria.

Moderation of engagement tools methods		
Brainstorming	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Arrange the setting for the participants, based on the size of the group. • Provide the participants the database of evaluation criteria in printed or digital version for the session. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prepare beforehand the following materials: whiteboard(s) or A0 poster(s), sticky notes, markers. • Moderate the session, encouraging participants to develop their ideas, writing their selection of evaluation criteria from the database, or their own ideas, on sticky notes, collecting them all in whiteboard(s). • Moderate the brainstorming session, encouraging all the stakeholders to participate. • Encourage participants to come up also with their own ideas, outside the database. • Keep track on the time, ensuring that also units of measurements and the direction of preference (min-max) will also be discussed and agreed from the participants (see Table 13 of the main document). • In case of large group of participants, divide the group into sub-groups, assign one moderator per sub-group to lead the discussion and adjust the time accordingly. Allow at least 30 min at the end for final reflection and consensus on the findings.
Round Tables		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Divide the group of participants in sub-groups and assign one moderator per sub-group. • Ask participants to discuss in their sub-groups the evaluation criteria given by the database and encourage them to add their own ideas as well. • Allow each sub-group to select their evaluation criteria (1-2 hours). • Keep track on the time, ensuring that also units of measurements and the direction of preference (min-max) will also be discussed and agreed from the participants (see Table 13 of the main document). • Once every sub-group has finalized their matrix, bring all participants together and ask them to discuss upon their results. Allow at least 1-2 hours for this step of the tool.

Moderation of engagement tools methods	
World Café	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Divide the group of participants in sub-groups and assign one moderator per sub-group. • Ask participants to discuss in their sub-groups the evaluation criteria given by the database and encourage them to add their own ideas as well. • Allow each sub-group to select their evaluation criteria (approx. 20 minutes). • Once the first round of 20 minutes is finished, ask participants to move to another sub-group, ensuring that at least one participant stays in the same sub-group of the first round, acting as a host for the next round. • Keep track on timing, making sure that the all the participants have passed from all the sub-groups. Allow at least 1 hour at the end for final reflection and consensus on the findings.

Table 5: Moderation of engagement tools and methods for Step 4: Scoring or assessment of options.

Moderation of engagement tools methods	
Expert Panels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide invited experts the list of the evaluation criteria identified in Step 2. • Organize the invited experts in panel, providing clear instruction on the impacts they must evaluate based on the criteria. • Allow experts to work as required, ensuring that the overall time of the step will not exceed half a day.
Focus Group Discussion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Once the experts panel is finished with the evaluation, bring participants into the session, allowing a common discussion, in a Focus-Group Discussion format (see Steps 0 and 2 for the moderation). For this step it is preferable to have all the stakeholders in one group with the experts, regardless the size of the (participants) group.

Table 6: Moderation of engagement tools and methods for Step 5: Weighting of evaluation criteria.

Moderation of engagement tools methods	
Focus Group Discussion (with experts' participation)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Arrange the setting for the participants, based on the size of the group, so that can all see each other during the discussion. • Invite experts to join the group(s) for the discussion, providing their input. • In case of large group of participants, divide the group into sub-groups, and assign one moderator per sub-group to lead the discussion. • Prepare beforehand the template for the weighting of the evaluation criteria (see Table 15 of the main document). • Ask participants to discuss upon the evaluation criteria, assigning weights to them. • Allow/ask all participants to provide their input for the weighting. • Keep track on the timing, ensuring that the template will be filled out on time for all the identified evaluation criteria. • Allow time for the participants to observe and the final results on the weighting (at least 30 min). • In case of sub-groups, allow time at the end (approx. 1 hour) for comparing the matrices reflecting upon and comparing the results. • Make sure that you get consensus among participants (both stakeholders and experts) for the weighting.

Table 7: Moderation of engagement tools and methods for Step 6: Ranking and prioritization of actions.

Moderation of engagement tools methods	
Focus Group Discussion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Arrange the setting for the participants, based on the size of the group, so that can all see each other during the discussion. • In case of large group of participants, divide the group into sub-groups, and assign one moderator per sub-group to lead the discussion. • Prepare beforehand the following: the template for the final scoring and ranking of the selected EbA options (see Table 16 of the main document), a 2x2 prioritization matrix (importance/urgency) on whiteboard or A0 paper, and sticky notes with all the selected EbA option (one option per sticky note). • Explain to the participants how the matrix should be filled in (see steps in Part 4. Step-by-step Guidelines for the MCA, Step 6). • Ask participants to discuss upon the final scoring and ranking of the selected EbA options.
Prioritization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Make sure that you get consensus among participants for the findings, ending up with a common template table. • Provide participants the prioritization matrix and ask them to place the sticky notes with the EbA option in the matrix. • Allow/ask all participants to provide their input for the prioritization. • Allow time for the participants to observe and discussed the results (at least 30 min). • In case of sub-groups, allow time at the end (approx. 1 hour) for comparing the matrices reflecting upon and comparing the results.

